

SUPERSHINE

D1.1: Landscape of sites socio-economic context

Authors: Paola Zerilli (UoY), Ahmed Djeddi (UoY), Riccardo Coletta (APRE), Flaminia Rocca (APRE)

Contributors: Alice Pittini (HE)

Technical references

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Authors	Paola Zerilli (UoY), Ahmed Djeddi (UoY), Riccardo Coletta (APRE)
Contributors	Alice Pittini (HE)
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Executive summary and abbreviations

The current document, titled SUPERSHINE Landscape of sites socio-economic context, has been developed within the framework of the SUPERSHINE project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under **Grant Agreement N° 101079963**.

Abbreviation, Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
AYMING	AYMING ITALIA S.r.l.
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (project coordinator)
ATER	Azienda Territoriale per L'Edilizia Residenziale di Trieste
BL	Boligselskabernes Landsforening
CARTIF	Fundacion Cartif
CIRCE	Fundacion CIRCE Centro de Investigacion De Recursos y Consumos Energeticos
DEMIR	De Surdurulebilir Enerji Ve Insaat Sanayi Ticaret Limited Sirketi
EC	European Commission
EEIP	Energy Efficiency in Industrial Processes ASBL
EGC	European Green Cities APS
ENA	Agencia de Energia e Ambiente da Arrabida
FB	Faellesbo
HE	Comité Europeen de Coordination de l'Habitat Social AISBL
ICONS	Fondazione ICONS
INSME	Rete Internazionale per le Piccole e Medie Imprese
KM	Kadikoy Belediyesi
GA	Grant Agreement
GAS	General Assembly
GC	General Committee (all partners participating)
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MQP	Management and Quality Plan
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project meeting
PO	Project Officer
REA	Riga Municipal Agency "RIGA ENERGY AGENCY"
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SP	Spacetime LLC
SG	Steering Group
TENDER	Tendercapital Alternative Funds PLC
TL	Task Leader
UoY	UNIVERSITY OF YORK (associated partner)
ZV	Sociedad Municipal Zaragoza Vivienda SL
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Project Overview

The objectives and impacts of the **SUPERSHINE project** will assist and support the European Commission to implement the **European Green Deal**. Particular attention will be paid to the **renovation of social housing**, to help households who struggle to pay their energy bills.

In addition, SUPERSHINE will also contribute to the **decrease of energy poverty**. The **three SUPERSHINE lighthouse districts (Denmark, Italy and Latvia)** will be characterised by energy efficient buildings, low carbon mobility, smart grids, efficient water and waste management, all underpinned by responsive technologies that optimise resources while promoting wellbeing and sustainable lifestyles.

Furthermore, SUPERSHINE solutions will be transferred from “ready to go projects” developed in the Lighthouse Cities to the **Fellow Cities of the Project, in Portugal, Serbia, Spain and Turkey**.

More specifically, SUPERSHINE will adopt an integrated strategy with these **key principles**:

- a) ‘Energy efficiency first’;
- b) Affordability;
- c) Decarbonisation and integration of renewables;
- d) Life-cycle thinking and circularity;
- e) High health and environmental standards by promoting sustainable energy behaviours;
- f) Tackling the twin challenges of the green and digital transitions together;
- g) Respect for aesthetics and architectural quality.

The main **areas of intervention** are:

- ❖ Strengthening information and incentives for public and private owners and tenants to undertake renovations while improving community participation or inspiring new patterns of citizen behaviour;
- ❖ Ensuring adequate and well-targeted funding by supporting innovative bottom up financial solutions such as Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) and Green Public Procurement (GPP) and collaborating with innovative local Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs);
- ❖ Promoting comprehensive and integrated renovation interventions;
- ❖ Making the construction ecosystem fit to deliver sustainable renovation, based on circular solutions, use and reuse of sustainable materials, and the integration of nature-based solutions while reducing whole life-cycle carbon emissions.

Introduction

According to Gangale and Mengolini, (2019), over 50 million people in the EU are affected by energy poverty which means that 7% of the EU population are affected by the high cost of energy bills to the point that it interferes with their physical and mental well-being. Additionally, 40% of the total energy consumption in Europe and 34% of the greenhouse gas emissions are contributed by the energy consumption of social and affordable buildings in the EU (European commission (2020)). The current energy crisis accompanied by the political distress in the Eastern Europe area have added significantly to the increase in electricity and gas prices which has affected the livelihood of millions of households in the EU, and since the global expansion in early 2020 of the COVID-19 pandemic, the energy crisis has exponentially increased the pre-existing issues of energy poverty in social and affordable housing, as inhabitants in EU countries enforcing lockdowns were more likely to spend more time at home increasing their energy consumption and became more vulnerable to energy poverty. According to a recent study by Siksnyte-Butkiene (2022), the COVID-19 pandemic has worsened the energy poverty in Europe by reducing disposable income while raising the energy costs. Also, by taking into account the energy-income rate, the European Commission suggested a recovery plan for Europe in 2020 to finance the **Renovation Wave** and update the energy infrastructure in EU buildings and the overcrowded districts.

Currently, multiple initiatives are being implemented at European level to diminish the net greenhouse gas emissions, and decouple the economic growth from resource consumption. These programs ensure that individuals who lack the financial capabilities to adopt a sustainable lifestyle that aligns with environmental objectives are not excluded (European Commission, (2022)). Furthermore, the European Council (2022) has introduced the revised 'Fit for 55' program, which establishes ambitious objectives for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the European Union and promoting the utilisation of renewable energy sources. ***The SUPERSHINE project focuses on building renovations, with the aim of enhancing energy efficiency in social housing.*** The inclusion of affordable and sustainable energy sources is an integral component of the overarching objectives outlined by the United Nations (2022), there are three specific targets associated with these objectives. These targets include achieving universal access to modern energy services, increasing the proportion of renewable energy sources, and enhancing energy efficiency by the year 2030. However, to achieve these targets the allocation of funds towards energy research, technological advancements, infrastructure development, and renovation is necessary.

The European Commission allocates financial resources for energy retrofit initiatives through various channels, such as the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and Cohesion Funds. The financial resources allocated under the framework of the European Structural and Investment (ESI) funds are directed towards the establishment of "sustainable and healthy European economies and environments" (European Commission, (2022)). The primary focus of the ERDF 2021-2027 is centred on the enhancement of a competitive and intelligent European territory, while simultaneously fostering a greener and low-carbon transition towards achieving a net zero carbon economy. This strategic approach aims to contribute to the development of a more resilient Europe. In practical terms, it is anticipated that around 30% of cash allocated by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and 37% of financing provided by the Cohesion Fund will be used towards climate-related objectives. These objectives encompass addressing energy poverty, implementing energy conservation initiatives, and migrating to energy-efficient technologies (EU (2021)).

Households experiencing energy poverty frequently face two issues. Firstly, they encounter inadequate heating/cooling or electrical systems that burn energy at an inefficient rate, leading to overconsumption of energy resources. Secondly, they endure the burden of high expenses related to energy overconsumption. In other words, those who are already residing in precarious conditions are compelled to confront supplementary hardships. According to Thomson et al. (2019), individuals residing in such circumstances may

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exhibit excessive energy consumption, leading to unaffordable utility bills. Conversely, they may engage in energy conservation practices to mitigate financial burdens, resulting in inadequate heating during winter months, insufficient cooling during summer months, or insufficient energy supply for daily necessities. These measures impose a psychological and emotional burden on the inhabitants. The prevalence of energy poverty frequently arises from the state of older housing stock in Europe, namely those built in the 1970s and 1980s. This situation results in a significant proportion of energy-inefficient dwellings, particularly within the social housing sector. As to the European Commission's findings, a significant proportion of buildings inside the European Union, specifically 75%, have been classified as possessing inadequate energy efficiency (European Commission (2020)).

The absence of sustainable housing has detrimental effects on all other facets of human existence. Several recent studies have indicated that the COVID-19 pandemic has disproportionately impacted disadvantaged families in terms of energy poverty, hence highlighting the significance of enhancing energy efficiency as both an environmental concern and a matter of social equity (Siksnyte-Butkiene, (2022)). The efforts towards enhancing energy efficiency in social housing are a response to the social, environmental, and economic challenges arising from the energy crisis in Europe. These endeavours take into account the needs of vulnerable households who benefit from such initiatives, the financial responsibilities of the city and its residents, and the enduring environmental consequences of energy production and usage. The implementation of energy-efficient measures in social housing presents a viable approach to addressing the underlying causes of energy poverty, as opposed to solely providing financial assistance for existing energy systems or implementing superficial solutions that may provide temporary relief but fail to resolve the issue in the long run (Vurro et al., 2022). **Hence, the SUPERSHINE project aims to enhance the well-being of individuals by concurrently improving the living conditions of households and reducing the environmental footprint associated with home energy consumption, particularly in terms of greenhouse gas emissions.** Through this action, the project actively contributes to the gradual transformation of the discourse around social housing and the issue of energy poverty in Europe. This deliverable comprises two main components. Firstly, an examination is conducted on the present state of energy poverty, as well as an exploration of the existing and innovative financing schemes in the SUPERSHINE lighthouse countries (Denmark, Italy, and Latvia), SUPERSHINE fellow countries (Serbia, Turkey, Portugal, and Spain), and the SUPERSHINE partner country (United Kingdom). Secondly, an analysis is carried out on the responses received from the SUPERSHINE lighthouse surveys.

Country specific EE oriented analysis of the local social housing sector

The European social housing sector has evolved over time, with each country adopting distinct approaches to address the housing needs of vulnerable populations. Social housing plays a critical role in alleviating energy poverty, ensuring affordable housing, and fostering social cohesion across Europe. However, the challenges faced by each country differ due to variations in legislation, funding mechanisms, and local circumstances. In this analysis, we examine the state of social housing and energy poverty in several European countries, focusing on their specific policies, funding frameworks, and the roles of various stakeholders involved. Drawing on insights from *Housing Europe (2012) "The Nuts and Bolts of European Social Housing Systems"*, we explore how different nations manage and improve their social housing sectors to support their citizens effectively.

Denmark

What is social housing? In Denmark, the concept of social housing consists of residential units that are made available for rent by non-profit housing groups. The Danish social housing model has a distinctive characteristic known as the principle of tenants democracy. This principle entails the organisation of the management and administration of each housing estate, wherein inhabitants have a key role in decision-making processes and overall governance. At present, non-profit housing constitutes around 20% of the overall housing inventory inside the nation.

Who provides social housing? Non-profit housing organisations have been responsible for the provision of social housing since the beginning of the 20th century. There exists an approximate total of 700 housing associations, possessing ownership of around 8000 properties. The ownership and organisation of these entities are jointly managed by the social housing association, while being subject to legal regulations imposed by the state.

How is social housing financed? Typically, a project is funded in the following manner: The housing association obtains 91% of its capital from borrowing from banks. The municipality contributes 7% of the total cost by providing an interest-free loan for the base capital and also offers guarantees for a portion of the mortgage. The remaining 2% is funded through deposits made by renters. In addition, renters who require financial assistance in meeting their rental obligations have access to specific housing allowances provided by the municipality. In Denmark, the financial framework for social housing incorporates a revolving fund mechanism. According to legislation, social housing units are mandated to be leased at cost rentals, which are determined based on historical expenditure. There is no reduction in rents upon the redemption of mortgage loans. In contrast, the generated revenue is allocated to the National Building Fund, which was formed in 1966. This fund is utilised by non-profit housing organisations for the purpose of conducting renovation projects and, more recently, to facilitate the financing of new building construction.

Who can access social housing? The waiting lists are accessible to anyone who has reached a minimum age of 15 years. The allocation of most unoccupied apartments is determined by the corresponding housing associations, taking into account the duration of time an individual has been on the waiting list as well as the size of their household. While recipients do not face income restrictions, there are certain limitations in place regarding the expenses of construction, which therefore affect rental rates, as well as the size of the residences. Moreover, the distribution of residences is subject to priority criteria that are established according to local circumstances. These criteria may include giving preference to certain groups such as families with children, individuals with disabilities, refugees, elderly individuals, students, divorced individuals, and those who require proximity to their workplace. In socioeconomically disadvantaged regions characterised by high rates of unemployment, it may be advantageous to prioritise those who serve as "role

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models," such as employed individuals or students. In some instances, towns possess the authority to allocate tenants to a minimum of 25% of unoccupied housing association units. Additionally, in collaboration with the housing association, municipalities have, on occasion, retained the prerogative to provide approval for all tenant assignments. In the event of direct distribution by the municipality, it is not necessary for recipients to be enrolled on a waiting list.

Italy¹

What is social housing? A definition of social housing first occurred in Italy in 2008, where social housing refers to a form of housing provision that is primarily aimed at meeting the needs of individuals or households that are unable to afford adequate housing in the private market. Social housing primarily consists of apartments rented on a long-term basis. Additionally, dwellings that are constructed or renovated through a combination of public and private resources or with the aid of public funding and are rented for a minimum of eight years or sold at an affordable price, are also classified as social housing. The overarching objective of social housing is to foster a diverse and inclusive community. Currently, social housing constitutes around 4% of the overall housing inventory in the nation. There exist three primary categories of publicly funded housing, namely subsidized housing (*edilizia sovvenzionata*), aided housing (*edilizia agevolata*), and agreed housing (*edilizia convenzionata*).

Who provides social housing? The public sector is primarily represented by the International Association of Chiefs of Policy (IACP), which was established in 1903 as governmental entities and has since evolved into independent public institutions with varying legislative frameworks. The organisation oversees a portfolio of publicly owned social housing properties, with a primary focus on serving households with little financial resources. Municipalities possess social and affordable houses, and they also assume direct management responsibilities. Regarding the public sector, it is noteworthy that despite the construction of more than one million residences throughout the post-war era, the public sector did experience a substantial expansion. This may be attributed to the ongoing trend of selling off considerable portions of the housing stock. Since 1978, the supply of social housing has seen the active participation of housing cooperatives and various corporate entities. In recent times, there has been an emergence of additional participants in the social housing sector, mostly in the form of foundations for social housing development. These entities have been established by collaborations between the banking institutions and various stakeholders such as Regions, Municipalities, and social housing companies. Various suppliers are engaged in diverse housing initiatives, as the responsibility for providing subsidized housing lies within the purview of the public sector, specifically municipalities and public housing agencies. The provision of social housing, on the other hand, has predominantly been undertaken by cooperatives. Both private and public entities participate in the provision of agreed-upon housing, with building construction firms being the most actively involved.

How is social housing financed? The primary responsibility for macro planning and co-financing of projects lies with the central government. This includes the provision of housing allowances, co-funding of urban redevelopment schemes, and assistance for social rental housing initiatives. The National Housing Plan has recently established the groundwork for novel public-private collaborations by introducing an integrated real estate fund. This fund comprises a national fund and a network of local revolving funds, with the primary objective of providing financial support for social housing initiatives. Only a limited number of funds of this nature have been established thus far. However, this specific financing modality signifies a significant change, as well as a challenge, especially for the public sector. The allocation of public money exhibits variability contingent upon the distinct classifications of publicly subsidised housing.

Who can access social housing? The primary objective of social housing in Italy is to fulfil a public interest by promoting social cohesion and addressing the housing challenges faced by marginalised individuals and families who lack access to housing within the conventional market. It is the obligation of regional authorities to establish the criteria for eligibility to access social housing, as well as to establish regulations governing

¹ <https://www.oecd.org/social/social-housing-policy-brief-2020.pdf>

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the determination of rental rates. The eligibility for public social housing is determined by a predefined set of requirements for registration on waiting lists throughout all regions in Italy. The factors that are considered in this context include the income of the applicants, their residence (specifically, if there exists an occupational or residential connection with the municipality), and their nationality. Preference is granted to those residing in substandard living circumstances, families with several dependents, or individuals facing involuntary cohabitation when it comes to receiving social housing.

Latvia²

What is social housing? It is often administered by government entities or non-profit organisations within Latvia, the provision of social housing includes both social homes and social flats, which are made available for rent by municipalities at reasonable rates to households who are considered vulnerable. A social apartment refers to a residential unit that is held by the local government and is allocated to a family that has been officially identified as eligible to lease the unit. Contracts are limited to a duration of up to six months and may be subject to renewal contingent upon the continued adherence of the household to the terms stipulated by the municipality. Moreover, social homes are buildings that are owned by the municipality and possess a distinct social standing, wherein all of the individual units within these buildings are designated as social flats. Social housing is a very small proportion of the municipal housing inventory, accounting for a little 0.4% of the overall national housing supply, with a notable concentration in major urban centres.

Who provides social housing? In Latvia, the provision of social housing is solely undertaken by municipalities. Nevertheless, several bigger cities have established dedicated social housing associations to undertake the operation and maintenance costs of public stock.

How is social housing financed? The allocation of funds for social housing is the responsibility of local authorities, who finance these initiatives through their own municipal budgets. Since 2006, the federal government has provided co-financing for investment in new social housing through dedicated funds. The subsidy program further promotes the establishment of public-private partnerships in the realm of social housing construction and repair. However, the engagement of private players has been notably limited thus far. The lessees pay a monthly rental fee that is quite modest, amounting to a maximum of one-third of the municipally established rent threshold. Frequently, the local government provides financial assistance to low-income households in the form of subsidies for utility expenses.

Who can access social housing? The access conditions for social housing in Latvia are delineated in local decrees enacted by the respective local municipalities, with the intended beneficiaries being households with low income.

Portugal³

What is social housing? The term "social housing" is predominantly employed by authorities and institutional entities in Portugal, encompassing a legal framework established by legislation in 1983. This legislation defines social housing as residential properties that are constructed and acquired with financial assistance from the State, facilitated through fiscal incentives and funding for land acquisition, construction, and housing development. The scope of this includes the supply of housing intended for purchase or rental by individuals or families with incomes below a designated threshold. Additionally, it encompasses measures that are tailored towards certain demographic groups that are the focus of housing and urban regeneration

²https://issuu.com/oecd.publishing/docs/latvia_housing_report_web1#:~:text=However%2C%20at%20less%20than%202,the%20poorest%20households%20in%202017.

³https://vbn.aau.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/328956623/Planaffho_2019_SALves_Final.pdf

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initiatives. This duty can be undertaken by many entities, including public agencies such as municipalities and central government, cooperatives, private institutions, and social organisations. Social housing comprises around 3.3% of the overall housing inventory in the country.

Who provides social housing? In Portugal, there are promoters and managers of social housing in many sectors, including the public sector, cooperative sector, and voluntary sector/non-profit organisations. In Portugal, social housing is mostly provided by municipalities, either directly or through Municipal Housing Companies. The public sector includes many entities engaged in the supply of social housing, including the Institute for Housing and Urban Renewal (IHRU) and regional authorities like the IHM and EPERAM in Madeira. Housing associations, which get financial support from the government, offer housing options at subsidised prices. In the nonprofit sector, there are organisations that, while not primarily focused on providing social housing, engage in this endeavour due to historical factors or fundamental reasons related to their core activities. Typically, social homes are allocated within designated areas or targeted towards certain disadvantaged groups. Social housing supply does not entail the participation of private landlords operating for profit.

How is social housing financed? Social housing is a decentralised authority within Municipal Councils, with programs derived from the Government (IHRU) through initiatives that aid municipal or cooperative enterprises. The financial contribution of the investment in buildings is often given by municipalities through IHRU, hence offering support. Cooperatives typically get comparable assistance from IHRU Plus, particularly where there are established cooperation procedures aimed at supporting towns. This help is commonly provided through the allocation of land for building purposes, typically for a specified duration. The existing funding mechanism for social housing in Portugal is deemed unsustainable due to a lack of enough public assistance and the prevalence of low rentals that fail to sufficiently pay building expenses.

Who can access social housing? There are various programmes in Portugal which contain different kinds of criteria for eligibility and priority to access to social housing:

- **PER Rehousing Programme**⁴ that gives priority to people living in shanty towns in the major metropolitan urban areas
- **Porta 65 Jovem**⁵ – support for young people to access rented housing. One of the criteria for granting this allowance is that the gross monthly income of the household “should be adequate to the interval between 1 and 4 times the maximum rent admitted in the area”.
- **Urban Rehabilitation Programmes**⁶ that concern the rehabilitation of rented buildings/dwellings which were affected by the long period of rental freezing and therefore suffered severe degradation.
- **NRAU**⁷ – the **New Urban Renting Regime** establishes a housing rent allowance benefiting low-income households with rental contracts prior to 1990, to counteract the updating of frozen housing rents.

Spain⁸

What is social housing? In Spain, the provision of social housing is primarily facilitated by the Vivienda de Protección Pública (publicly protected housing) program. The housing model in question has a distinctive

⁴ Elena Tarsi (2020), A critical perspective on policies for informal settlements in Portugal, *Cities*, Volume 107, 102949, ISSN 0264-2751, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102949>.

⁵ <https://eportugal.gov.pt/en/servicos/candidatar-se-ao-porta-65-jovem#:~:text=The%20E2%80%9CPorta%2065%2DJovem%2%80%9D%20is%20an%20incentive%20programme%20to,element%20may%20not%20exceed%2034>.

⁶ João Igreja, Paulo Conceição. (2021) The influence of EU policy on local policy-making, governance and urban change. Evidence from Porto, Portugal. *Urban Research & Practice* 14:4, pages 372-396.

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/30669/attachments/2/translations/en/renditions/native>

⁸ Alberdi, B. (2014). Social Housing in Spain. In Social Housing in Europe (eds K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead and M.F. Arrigoitia). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118412367.ch13>

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characteristic when compared to social housing models prevalent in the majority of European Union nations, since it primarily caters to owner-occupancy. Merely a limited fraction of the expanding housing stock is available for rental purposes. One salient feature of protected housing entails the provision of financial support from the State in the form of lower interest loans to facilitate the building, repair, and acquisition of such properties by eligible providers. As a result of this arrangement, residences that adhere to specific criteria regarding dimensions and standards are offered for sale or rent at prices that are lower than the prevailing market rates, only to individuals whose incomes fall below specified thresholds. The housing market in Spain is predominantly characterised by home-ownership, which accounts for around 85% of the total housing stock. In contrast, the rental sector is very modest compared to other European countries, comprising just 11% of the total housing stock. Furthermore, the rental market is primarily focused in major cities such as Barcelona and Madrid. Approximately 2% of the portfolio consists of social rental housing.

Who provides social housing? governmental support for protected housing encompasses a wide range of sources, including governmental developers, commercial developers, not-for-profit organisations, cooperatives, and people seeking to purchase or restore a property either individually or collectively.

How is social housing financed? Protected housing mostly receives financial support from the National Housing Plan, supplemented by regional plans, and also relies on borrowing from commercial credit institutions to a lesser level. The state enters into agreements with credit institutions, who undertake to provide loans under favourable terms. In addition to the provision of advantageous loans, certain instances of protected housing may also receive direct state assistance in the form of grants or loan subsidies.

Who can access social housing?⁹ Based on income distribution depending on the specific category of VPO (Vivienda de Protección Oficial, or Officially Protected Housing), a significant proportion of households, up to over 80%, may be considered to possess virtual accessibility to this particular form of housing. The individual who acquires or constructs a residential property for personal occupancy must satisfy the following criteria: they should not possess or hold a permanent entitlement to utilize another residence, they should not have received financial assistance from the Housing Plan within the preceding decade, and their income should fall below a certain threshold. Individuals with disabilities and those who are reliant on others are given precedence, while regional authorities have the ability to impose additional criteria.

United Kingdom (UK)

What is social housing? Social housing in the United Kingdom refers to the provision of affordable housing that is assigned based on the principle of need with the exception of Northern Ireland, where social housing is only available for rental purposes, the remainder of the United Kingdom includes a broader range of social housing options. These options include the supply of rental residencies, affordable home ownership opportunities, and shared ownership plans. The provision of housing is often facilitated by local governing bodies and non-profit entities, such as housing associations. However, it is important to note that there may be variations in this arrangement across different nations, as elaborated upon in the subsequent discussion. In England, social housing constitutes around 17.5% of the overall residential properties, but in Scotland, it comprises over 24% of the entire housing stock. In Northern Ireland, social housing represents approximately 17% of the housing inventory, while in Wales, it accounts for approximately 16.4%.

Who provides social housing? The significant decrease in the construction of council houses, coupled with the sale of properties to existing tenants and the transfer of more than one million local authority dwellings to housing associations from 1988 to 2009, has resulted in housing associations becoming the primary providers of affordable housing in England. Presently, they oversee the management of 54% of social housing. A reduction in the public provision of social housing has also been observed in Scotland and Wales. However, it is worth noting that in Scotland, the housing stock owned by local authorities remains larger than that owned by registered social landlords. In contrast, in Wales, the social housing sector is evenly divided

⁹ The Spanish association of public social housing and land providers (AVS) www.promotorespublicos.org

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between local authorities and registered social landlords. The situation in Northern Ireland diverges in that there was an absence of a comprehensive transfer of public homes to housing associations on a significant scale. In contrast, the domiciles of the residents were subsequently transferred by local authorities to the Northern Ireland Housing Executive, an entity that serves as the strategic housing authority for Northern Ireland. Presently, this organisation is responsible for the management of more than two-thirds of the social housing inventory within the territory.

How is social housing financed? The financing of new social housing and its land expenses is provided by three primary funding sources: housing association reserves, government grants, and private finance. Private finance often includes bank loans or funds acquired via capital market activities. Before 2007, the growth of social leased housing was supported by cross subsidies derived from the supply of low-cost home ownership. However, in the aftermath of the global financial crisis, the prospects for such activities have significantly decreased. The coordination of capital subsidies is carried out by the devolved governments, including the Homes and Communities Agency in England, the Housing and Regeneration directorate of the Scottish Government, the Housing Directorate of the Welsh Assembly Government, and the Northern Ireland Housing Executive. In addition, social housing also receives advantages in the form of reduced land costs and development contributions through the implementation of "section 106" rules. These laws mandate the inclusion of a certain percentage of affordable housing in significant development projects. The occupants of social leased dwellings are obligated to remit a weekly rental fee that is significantly lower than the prevailing market rate (in 2007, the rental charges for social housing were, on average, around 56% of the market rental prices). The rental prices of properties are influenced by the valuation of each particular property, as well as the income levels within the surrounding region. These rentals are subject to periodic increases based on a predetermined formula. Tenants may potentially qualify for Housing Benefits, which are managed by local authorities, to cover either the entirety or a portion of their monthly rent, contingent upon meeting the criteria of a means test. Indeed, there has been a notable shift in the allocation of subsidies between supply side and demand side in the realm of individual housing benefits in recent decades.

Who can access social housing? Regarding the recipients of social housing, it is important to note that following the enactment of the Housing Act of 1977, all local authorities in the United Kingdom are theoretically mandated to offer housing to individuals experiencing housing insecurity, provided they satisfy specific objective criteria and align with the designated priority groups to be supported. Social housing is primarily intended for individuals or groups within the population who are considered vulnerable, with certain categories, such as individuals experiencing homelessness, being granted legal precedence. The Homelessness Scotland Act, which was enacted by the Scottish Parliament in 2003, is a legislative measure that surpasses the provisions of the Housing Act of 1977. Starting from 2012, Scottish individuals who are experiencing inadequate housing conditions will have the opportunity to initiate legal proceedings in order to get permanent dwelling from their respective local councils, provided that their application for permanent accommodation remains unresolved.

Serbia¹⁰

What is social housing? Serbia has a history of social housing dating back to the socialist era when the government provided social housing for the vulnerable workers and their families. However, the transition to a market economy in the 1990s led to a decline in state funded housing initiatives which led to a significant shortage of social housing units, leaving many vulnerable individuals and families without access to affordable housing. Currently, social housing in Serbia is suffering from poor quality of existing social housing units which affects the overall quality of life for the inhabitants, and the complex administrative procedures in the allocation of social housing makes it difficult for those in need to access these services. However, the governing body of Serbia along with social housing associations have implemented legislative reforms aimed at improving the social housing sector through providing a clearer criteria for eligibility and a more

¹⁰ Belgarde Center for Human Rights (2020) "Social housing in Serbia: An overview"

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transparent allocation process. Also, there is a growing interest in public-private partnerships to fund and develop social housing projects which can help the supply of good quality affordable houses to the vulnerable population.

Who provides social housing? Social housing in Serbia is primarily provided through a combination of government agencies and the private sector. The key entities involved in providing social housing in Serbia are:

- **Ministry of construction, transport and infrastructure:** This ministry oversees housing policies, social housing programs and allocating resources for housing initiatives.
- **City and municipal housing authorities:** cities in Serbia have their own housing authorities responsible for managing and providing social housing within their jurisdictions.
- **Social housing associations:** the social housing entities in Serbia are responsible for managing and maintaining social housing units and ensure the existence of social housing stock is in good condition.

How is social housing financed? Social housing in Serbia is financed through combination of funding sources such as:

- **Government budget allocation:** where the Serbian government allocates funds through its national budget to finance various aspects of social housing, including the construction of new social housing units and the maintenance of existing units.
- **European Union Funds:** Serbia's effort to align with EU standards and pursue EU membership open up opportunities for funding from the European Union. The EU provides financial support for housing and urban development projects, including social housing initiatives.
- **Municipal contributions:** Local municipalities in Serbia have funds allocated to address the housing needs of their local residents.
- **Housing Funds and Foundation:** the **regional housing program**, provides financial support for affordable and social housing projects.

Turkey¹¹

What is social housing and who provides social housing? The concept of social housing in Turkey dates back to the early 1920s, when the Turkish government initiated various housing projects to address the housing needs of the poor population in urban cities which led the foundation to the modern social housing policies in Turkey. The Turkish government established the Mass Housing administration (TOKI) in 1984 for the purpose of planning and executing social housing projects across the country. The TOKI operated under the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization. The units built by the TOKI initiatives are then sold to low and middle income families at favourable terms. Additionally, TOKI has implemented rental housing projects to provide housing options for those who cannot afford to purchase a house. The social housing in Turkey has improved the living conditions for millions of residents which led to reduced homelessness, increased social cohesion and enhanced overall wellbeing of residents Kadioglu (2017)¹².

How is social housing financed? Social housing projects in Turkey are typically financed through a combination of sources, including government funds, loans and partnerships with the private sector. The Mass Housing Administration (TOKI) often collaborates with private sector developers and utilises various financial mechanisms to fund social housing initiatives.

¹¹ Turkish Ministry of Environment and Urbanization (2021). Annual housing report 2021.

¹² Kadioglu, A. (2017) The role of social housing in addressing housing affordability: a case study of Istanbul. International Journal of Housing Policy, 17(3), 431-451.

State Of The Art

Statistics on EE status for the social housing sector at country specific level with a focus on energy poverty

Following the guidelines by the **EU Energy Poverty Observatory (EUPO) online platform**¹³, the energy poverty indicators are organised into “**primary indicators**” and “**secondary indicators**”¹⁴. As indicated by the **EU Energy Poverty methodology Guidebook** the main **primary indicators** for energy poverty are:

1. [Percentage of population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status;](#)
2. [Arrears on utility bills;](#)
3. [Structure of consumption expenditure by income quintile and consumption purpose](#) (with a focus on the share of energy expenditure in income for the first quintile).

Among the **secondary indicators**, we find:

1. [Share of population living in a dwelling not comfortably cool during summertime by income quintile and degree of urbanisation;](#)
2. [Population at risk of poverty or social exclusion;](#)
3. [Material and social deprivation rate by tenure status;](#)
4. [Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation, or rot in window frames or floor;](#)
5. [Housing cost overburden rate by tenure status;](#)
6. [Overcrowding rate by tenure status.](#)

Additionally, the “[final energy consumption in households](#)” has been chosen as a proxy for indicators in the key area 'Improving buildings' of the resource efficiency initiative. This area focuses on the energy spent in households for heating purposes and how the amelioration of buildings can contribute to energy-saving plans. Using the **Eurostat Energy data** and the **Eurostat income and living conditions** datasets for the SUPER-i partner countries, relevant tables and charts for the above indicators are shown below. While the EU average rates of homes **unable to be kept adequately warm in winter** has fallen in the previous decade, of the 6 fellow countries progress has been strong only in Italy and Slovenia, with marginal progress in Belgium, and stasis in Denmark, Spain and the UK. A similar trend can be seen on the **arrears on bills** metric, though the ratios across the metrics are not similar, with e.g. nearly twice as many households in UK than Slovenia unable to keep their homes warm, but nearly three times as many households in Slovenia than that UK in utility bill arrears over the last decade. Similarly, these numbers may not agree with others reported by EUPO, or the measures used by the national governments; for example, according to the Italian government’s preferred energy poverty statistic: “*in the period 2005-2016 the proportion of households in energy poverty was, on average, approximately 8% of all households. However, the percentage has grown [to 2019] to about 8.6%*”¹⁵

¹³ https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/energy-poverty-observatory/indicators_en

¹⁴ Thema, J., and Vondung, F. (2020) EPOV Indicator Dashboard: Methodology Guidebook. Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie GmbH. https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/epov_methodology_guidebook_1.pdf

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/it_final_necp_main_en.pdf

Population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status

The tables and graphs below show the share of the population who are unable to keep their homes adequately warm, to monitor the development of poverty and social inclusion in the partner countries. In the case of the population with income status below 60% of the median equivalised income, we observe that residents in Turkey, Portugal and Latvia have the highest rates of energy poverty. However, we observe that overtime the share of the population unable to keep their homes warm has declined significantly over the last decade for Latvia from 40% to 12% in 2021 and rose to 18% in 2022 which can be explained by the increased inflation rate in the energy sector. Also, the other SUPERSHINE partner countries have experienced a reduction but not as significant as in the case of Latvia.

Table 1 - Population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status: above 60% of median equivalised income

Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	7.3	8.0	8.1	7.5	6.6	6.1	5.7	5.1	4.6			
Denmark	1.6	1.8	3.0	2.5	2.4	2.0	2.2	2.3	2.0	1.9	1.9	4.5
Italy	13.3	15.8	13.7	13.1	12.3	11.8	11.7	10.0	7.3	6.1	5.9	6.6
Latvia	18.2	16.3	17.7	13.0	10.3	7.3	6.7	5.1	5.7	4.0	2.6	3.8
Portugal	22.9	23.5	24.1	23.7	19.1	17.8	16.3	15.8	15.0	14.3	13.8	14.0
United Kingdom	5.5	5.9	8.5	7.2	5.6	4.5	4.6	4.0				
Serbia			14.5	13.7	11.6	10.4	10.1	6.9	7.0	4.8	4.7	
Turkey	29.0	30.1	20.4	9.3	7.3	17.3	13.4	11.9	12.5	13.7	13.6	
Spain	4.7	6.6	6.1	7.5	7.	6.3	4.9	5.9	4.4	7.9	10.5	14

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 1 - Population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status: above 60% of median equivalised income

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Table 2 - Population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status: below 60% of median equivalised income

Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	22.0	24.5	24.1	23.5	22.7	21.0	18.4	17.9	17.2			
Denmark	7.4	8.4	10.2	5.8	12.7	7.9	6.6	7.8	8.4	10.9	8.9	9.4
Italy	36.1	44.0	40.4	38.3	35.9	32.4	29.1	30.0	26.3	17.2	17.0	17.6
Latvia	40.8	35.1	35.5	31.0	29.1	22.7	20.3	15.4	15.9	13.2	12.4	18.3
Portugal	44.8	43.1	44.6	47.5	43.3	42.7	38.9	37.0	38.0	33.8	27.9	35.8
United Kingdom	11.4	19.2	21.7	20.2	18.6	14.2	12.4	11.8				
Serbia			30.0	27.2	25.2	21.6	21.7	19.4	19.7	26.2	27.1	
Turkey	56.3	59.9	58.7	36.1	45.8	47.6	46.4	44.3	42.4	42.6	44.5	
Spain	13.2	18.9	15.6	23.5	23.3	23.2	19.4	20.8	19.6	22.3	27.7	30

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 2 - Population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status: below 60% of median equivalised income

Table 3 - Population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status: overall

Country	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	9.8	10.8	10.7	10.3	9.4	8.7	7.8	7.3	6.7			
Denmark	2.3	2.5	3.8	2.9	3.6	2.7	2.7	3.0	2.8	3.0	2.8	5.1
Italy	17.8	21.3	18.8	18.0	17.0	16.1	15.2	14.1	11.1	8.3	8.1	8.8
Latvia	22.5	19.9	21.1	16.8	14.5	10.6	9.7	7.5	8.0	6.0	4.9	7.1
Portugal	26.8	27.0	27.9	28.3	23.8	22.5	20.4	19.4	18.9	17.5	16.4	17.5
United Kingdom	6.5	8.1	10.6	9.4	7.8	6.1	5.9	5.4				
Serbia			18.3	17.1	15.2	13.3	13.1	10.0	9.9	9.5	9.4	
Turkey	35.4	37.2	29.3	15.5	15.9	24.2	20.7	19.1	19.2	20.3	20.5	
Spain	6.5	9.1	8.	11.1	10.6	10.1	8.	9.1	7.5	10.9	14.2	17

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 3 - Population unable to keep home adequately warm by poverty status: overall

Arrears on utility bills

From the table and graph below, we observe that residents in Turkey, Serbia and Latvia have the highest arrears on utility bills compared to the other partner countries. Also, we observe that Denmark has the lowest rate of arrears on utility bills.

Table 4 - Arrears on utility bills

Country	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	10.2	9.9	9.1	8.1	7.0	6.6	6.1			
Denmark	3.6	4.6	3.4	2.5	3.5	5.1	3.6	4.2	2.9	3.5
Italy	11.9	12.2	12.6	8.9	4.8	4.5	4.5	6.0	6.5	5.0
Latvia	20.7	19.6	16.7	13.2	11.9	11.6	8.7	8.3	5.8	5.9
Portugal	8.2	8.5	7.8	7.3	5.6	4.5	4.3	3.5	5.3	4.7
United Kingdom	8.7	7.2	7.0	5.7	5.0	5.4				
Serbia	36.7	41.4	34.8	34.8	18.1	28.4	25.8	26.7	21.9	
Turkey	39.8	35.8	33.2	29.0	26.3	23.7	26.6	22.8	24.5	
Spain	8.3	9.2	8.8	7.8	7.4	7.2	6.5	9.6	9.5	9.2

Figure 4 - Arrears on utility bills

Share of population living in dwelling not comfortably cool during summer time

The table and graph below shows that Portugal, Latvia, Spain and Italy have a considerably higher percentage of population living in dwellings not comfortably cool during the summer compared to the other countries. While the UK and Denmark have the lowest rate. This could be related to the impact of cooler weather in the UK compared to the Mediterranean countries.

Table 5 - Share of population living in a dwelling not comfortably cool during summer time by income quintile

	Total	First quintile	Second quintile	Third quintile	Fourth quintile	Fifth quintile
European Union	19.1	25.1	21.1	18.5	16.4	14.4
Denmark	11.3	10.7	13.6	10.7	13.2	8.2
Italy	26.0	36.9	29.2	24.7	21.4	17.7
Latvia	29.9	31.7	30.7	31.0	30.5	25.8
Portugal	35.7	41.2	36.3	38.3	35.3	27.4
United Kingdom	3.3	4.0	4.4	2.9	3.3	1.9
Spain	25.6	36.7	30.7	24.6	20.2	15.7

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 5 - Share of population living in a dwelling not comfortably cool during summer time by income quintile

People at risk of poverty or social exclusion

The table and graph below shows the rate of population at risk of poverty or social exclusion in the past 8 years. Even Though the rates are comparable, we observe that the share of people in Latvia, Spain and Italy has the highest rate of possible poverty or social exclusion compared to the other European Union countries.

Table 6 - : People at risk of poverty and social exclusion

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	24.0	23.7	22.4	21.7	21.1	21.6	21.7	21.6
Denmark	18.6	17.5	17.8	17.5	17.3	16.8	17.3	17.1
Italy	28.4	27.8	25.9	25.7	24.6	24.9	25.2	24.4
Latvia	30.0	28.2	28.5	28.4	26.7	25.1	26.1	26.0
Portugal	26.4	24.9	23.4	21.6	21.1	20.0	22.4	20.1
Spain	28.7	28.8	27.5	27.3	26.2	27.0	27.8	26.0

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 6 - People at risk of poverty and social exclusion

Material and social deprivation rate

The table and graphs below show the material and social deprivation rate for owners with mortgage, owners without mortgage, tenants that pay rent at market value, and tenants that are paying subsidised rent or are rent free residents. From these statistics we observe that the material and social deprivation rates in the partner countries are comparable and higher than those at the European Union level, except for Denmark and the United Kingdom.

Table 7 - Material and social deprivation rate: all

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	19.7	17.5	16.0	14.0	13.1	12.5			
Denmark	6.7	7.7	6.3	7.5	8.1	7.1	6.6	5.9	6.8
Italy	23.2	22.0	17.5	12.7	12.7	11.9	11.0	11.3	9.0
Latvia	34.6	28.9	25.0	25.7	20.8	15.5	14.8	11.1	14.1
Portugal	27.0	22.2	19.0	17.0	14.6	13.2	12.7	13.5	11.9
United Kingdom	16.9	14.4	13.2	10.9	9.9				
Serbia	44.3	40.1		36.4	29.9	24.4	22.6	21.4	
Turkey				31.0	29.0	29.8	29.6	31.7	
Spain	20.5	16.3	17.6	15.0	15.3	14.0	15.4	15.4	15.4

Figure 7 - Material and social deprivation rate: all

Table 8 - Material and social deprivation rate: owner with outstanding mortgage or housing loan

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	10.6	8.7	7.4	5.6	5.5	5.2			
Denmark	2.9	3.1	2.7	2.8	3.3	2.3	2.1	1.6	2.6
Italy	19.6	16.7	12.2	6.6	8.2	7.3	8.4	9.0	6.6
Latvia	19.8	13.8	13.9	11.8	10.5	6.3	4.9	2.3	4.6
Portugal	19.6	15.0	12.2	10.9	9.0	7.1	7.1	9.2	7.4
United Kingdom	9.1	6.1	5.7	3.8	3.8				
Serbia	26.1	17.1		28.2	5.5	11.7	0.0	6.4	
Turkey				18.3	18.1	19.0	17.8	20.7	
Spain	20.	15.	15.1	9.7	10.5	9.3	10.6	12.6	13.0

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 8 - Material and social deprivation rate: owner with outstanding mortgage or loan

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Table 9 - : Material & social deprivation rate: owner without outstanding mortgage or loan

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	18.5	16.1	14.9	13.3	12.1	11.9			
Denmark	0.9	1.6	1.6	2.0	1.0	2.1	1.6	1.4	1.9
Italy	16.0	14.9	11.6	8.4	8.6	8.7	7.1	6.9	6.1
Latvia	32.7	27.3	22.9	24.9	18.8	14.3	13.0	10.3	13.2
Portugal	22.7	16.9	15.8	13.7	11.0	10.6	11.5	12.1	9.6
United Kingdom	3.8	2.0	2.1	1.9	2.1				
Serbia	44.4	39.6		36.2	29.2	22.7	22.1	20.7	
Turkey				27.8	25.5	24.7	25.3	27.2	
Spain	13.4	10.3	11.9	11.2	11.8	9.7	9.3	9.2	9.4

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 9 - Material & social deprivation rate: owner without outstanding mortgage or loan

Table 10 - Material and social deprivation rate by tenure status: tenants, rent at market value

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	27.0	25.2	23.3	20.2	20.4	18.5			
Denmark	14.1	15.9	12.5	15.8	16.5	14.6	13.5	12.1	13.2
Italy	44.4	44.7	34.8	27.3	25.9	20.9	24.1	23.5	16.4
Latvia	47.1	37.4	36.2	34.2	34.4	23.5	24.8	15.5	21.7
Portugal	44.5	40.3	34.3	27.5	24.2	23.3	23.2	27.1	24.1
United Kingdom	25.3	24.4	21.8	17.1	22.5				
Serbia	38.6	44.5		35.0	34.4	30.7	20.6	24.7	
Turkey				39.8	37.6	40.3	38.8	41.3	
Spain	38.2	32.3	33.0	29.3	28.7	27.7	36.5	33.4	31.8

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 10 - Material and social deprivation rate by tenure status: tenants, rent at market value

Table 11 - Material & social deprivation rate by tenure status: tenants, subsidised rent or rent free

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	38.6	34.4	33.2	31.4	27.2	25.3			
Denmark	52.1	44.4	47.7	40.7	34.2	34.5	35.8	37.1	30.0
Italy	62.8	57.3	51.8	49.5	47.3	35.2	38.5	37.8	40.9
Latvia	69.0	65.1	63.1	59.8	53.3	48.8	47.1	33.3	40.0
Portugal	46.5	40.5	37.5	35.9	31.6				
United Kingdom	55.0	38.3		44.3	43.6	13.4	21.0	28.0	
Serbia				3.3	2.3	2.0	3.9	7.4	
Spain	60.	51.3	59.1	50.1	44.5	45.2	34.3	37.3	38.1

Figure 11 - Material & social deprivation rate by tenure status: tenants, subsidised rent or rent free

Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation

The tables and graphs below show the share of the population living in poor condition dwellings for the period ranging from 2013 to 2020. Considering only the population with income below the 60% median equivalised income, we observe that Turkey has the highest population living in poor dwellings followed by Latvia and Portugal. Also we observe that except for the UK and Denmark, the population of partner countries living in poor condition is higher than that on the European Union level. However, in the case of Italy and Spain we observe a significant decrease in the share of people living in poor condition houses.

Table 12 - Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation: above 60% of median equivalised income

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
European Union	14.1	13.9	13.4	13.5	11.7	12.3	11.8	
Denmark	15.8	14.9	15.3	15.3	13.9	15.2	14.2	16.0
Italy	21.2	23.2	22.1	19.2	14.8	12.1	13.4	18.4
Latvia	23.8	24.3	20.3	17.6	19.2	19.5	16.1	14.9
Portugal	30.0	31.0	26.1	28.2	23.2	24.5	21.8	23.1
United Kingdom	15.5	15.2	13.4	15.4	15.9	16.1		
Serbia	17.9	22.9	20.6	18.4	17.3	12.6	15.1	8.5
Turkey	33.6	31.3	32.9	32.2	30.5	30.3	31.2	29.6
Spain	15.5	14.7	13.4	12.8	9.9	13.9	13.2	17.

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 12 - Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation: above 60% of median equivalised income

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Table 13 - Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation: below 60% of median equivalised income

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
European Union	23.5	24.6	24.0	24.6	21.1	21.9	20.3	
Denmark	23.1	16.3	22.2	20.1	22.0	24.9	19.6	22.3
Italy	30.1	32.8	32.2	27.7	21.4	17.6	16.4	24.5
Latvia	44.1	39.2	38.7	37.2	35.3	36.5	30.0	27.1
Portugal	40.1	40.2	36.6	40.1	35.7	38.3	36.5	36.4
United Kingdom	18.1	23.6	22.1	22.2	22.1	24.0		
Serbia	33.1	35.8	31.0	31.9	31.2	29.0	27.7	21.6
Turkey	60.2	56.8	60.1	58.1	57.9	56.8	56.7	51.9
Spain	21.7	25.4	21.3	26.7	17.5	23.2	20.7	29.7

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 13 - Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation: below 60% of median equivalised income

Table 14 - Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation: overall

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
European Union	15.6	15.7	15.2	15.4	13.3	13.9	13.2	
Denmark	16.6	15.0	16.1	15.9	14.9	16.4	14.9	16.8
Italy	22.9	25.0	24.1	21.0	16.1	13.2	14.0	19.6
Latvia	27.7	27.5	24.4	21.9	22.8	23.5	19.3	17.5
Portugal	31.9	32.8	28.1	30.5	25.5	26.9	24.4	25.2
United Kingdom	15.9	16.6	14.8	16.4	17.0	17.6		
Serbia	21.6	26.2	23.4	21.8	20.8	16.6	18.0	11.4
Turkey	39.7	37.2	39.0	38.1	36.6	36.2	36.9	34.7
Spain	16.7	17.1	15.2	15.9	11.5	15.9	14.7	19.7

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 14 - Total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation: overall

Housing cost overburden rate by tenure

The table and graphs below show the housing cost overburden rate for owners with mortgage, owners without mortgage, tenants that pay rent at market value, and tenants that are paying subsidised rent or are rent free residents. Considering only the owners with outstanding mortgage and tenants paying subsidised rent or are rent free, we observe that the housing cost overburden rate of Serbia is the highest followed by that of Latvia, while the other partner countries show a lower rate than that at the European Union level.

Table 15 - Housing cost overburden rate: owner with outstanding mortgage or loan

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	8.4	7.7	7.1	5.6	4.6	4.0	4.0	3.5	5.0	4.7
Denmark	7.5	5.2	5.3	5.2	5.5	5.2	5.3	6.1	4.6	3.9
Italy	6.7	5.5	4.8	4.6	3.6	3.3	3.2	1.9	2.2	2.1
Latvia	16.2	15.2	15.5	9.3	10.1	9.6	6.1	6.0	5.1	5.2
Portugal	6.8	7.4	6.6	4.4	3.9	3.0	2.7	2.2	3.9	1.4
United Kingdom	4.3	6.7	4.9	4.8	5.2	5.1				
Serbia	33.4	36.6	20.7	20.6	42.0	34.0	30.1	10.5	8.0	
Turkey	17.3	12.7	14.1	13.1	10.9	12.2	12.4	11.7	13.1	
Spain	8.2	9.	8.7	6.7	4.5	3.5	3.7	3.	3.7	3.2

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 15 - Housing cost overburden rate: owner with outstanding mortgage or loan

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Table 16 - Housing cost overburden rate: owner without outstanding mortgage or loan

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	7.4	7.1	7.0	6.6	6.0	5.5	5.3	4.2	4.7	5.2
Denmark	6.7	7.1	4.3	4.3	8.5	7.1	8.6	8.0	7.6	7.6
Italy	2.8	2.9	2.8	3.6	2.7	2.6	3.2	2.7	2.8	2.6
Latvia	9.9	8.2	6.2	5.8	5.8	5.8	4.9	3.8	4.1	4.8
Portugal	2.5	3.8	3.2	2.9	2.5	2.0	2.0	1.5	2.6	1.7
United Kingdom	1.5	4.1	3.9	4.3	4.2	7.0				
Serbia	25.2	29.5	31.8	28.7	31.0	28.9	19.4	16.5	14.2	
Turkey	1.5	1.0	1.5	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.3	2.5	2.0	
Spain	2.8	2.8	2.7	2.8	2.9	2.6	1.8	2.2	3.1	2.8

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 16 - Housing cost overburden rate: owner without outstanding mortgage or loan

Table 17 - Housing cost overburden rate: tenant, rent at market value

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	25.9	27.1	26.4	27.0	25.1	25.1	24.2	20.9	21.9	21.0
Denmark	37.1	32.9	31.9	31.6	31.7	28.9	30.7	25.2	30.3	29.5
Italy	34.2	32.4	32.7	32.2	28.2	29.1	29.2	28.1	26.2	25.9
Latvia	17.1	15.1	13.6	13.0	11.2	11.5	8.3	13.5	10.7	11.3
Portugal	35.2	33.8	35.4	31.9	28.2	25.8	26.3	19.7	26.9	29.4
United Kingdom	25.3	34.6	37.1	35.4	38.6	37.7				
Serbia	62.4	67.5	65.5	70.3	63.5	71.0	56.3	62.3	45.7	
Turkey	44.4	39.4	36.1	34.4	32.4	32.1	33.0	29.2	34.5	
Spain	42.3	47.5	43.3	43.	42.1	38.1	37.4	35.9	40.9	39.4

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

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Figure 17 - Housing cost overburden rate: tenant, rent at market value

Table 18 - Housing cost overburden rate: tenant, subsidised rent or free rent

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	11.6	11.3	11.1	12.1	12.2	10.2	10.7	8.5	11.8	14.2
Denmark										
Italy	10.9	10.5	9.9	12.7	10.7	8.3	9.6	7.3	7.5	5.1
Latvia	12.7	9.7	9.4	8.0	7.6	6.0	5.5	4.3	6.6	6.3
Portugal	6.3	6.7	7.6	5.4	5.7	4.9	4.0	3.5	3.9	4.2
United Kingdom	8.4	16.0	15.2	16.2	20.5	20.3				
Serbia	33.1	35.5	38.2	36.5	41.1	38.1	26.4	17.9	17.1	
Turkey	2.2	1.4	1.9	1.6	1.2	1.1	1.9	2.6	2.3	
Spain	9.5	10.8	9.9	10.6	13.1	10.1	9.3	8.2	11.5	11.5

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 18 - Housing cost overburden rate: tenant, subsidised rent or free rent

Overcrowding rate by tenure status

The table and graphs below show the overcrowding rate of owners with mortgage, owners without mortgage, tenants that pay rent at market value, and tenants that are paying subsidised rent or are rent free residents. Considering only the owners with outstanding mortgage and rent free tenants or those who pay subsidised rent, we observe that the overcrowding rate in Serbia, Turkey is the highest followed by Latvia.

Table 19 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: owner with mortgage or loan

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	8.8	8.2	8.6	8.4	8.2	7.8	8.0	8.1	8.5	8.3
Denmark	3.7	3.8	4.4	3.2	3.8	3.7	4.9	3.5	4.0	4.3
Italy	27.4	25.6	28.5	30.0	29.7	31.5	31.4	27.5	28.8	28.6
Latvia	24.6	28.7	31.2	29.7	35.7	40.8	37.8	34.1	38.3	37.2
Portugal	10.3	7.9	8.9	8.6	7.3	8.0	7.7	8.7	9.9	8.8
United Kingdom	4.3	3.4	3.2	4.2	2.0	2.4				
Serbia	53.9	62.2	54.8	70.6	53.1	53.3	49.1	47.3	74.3	
Turkey	28.7	29.6	33.0	31.4	30.3	29.9	30.5	30.6	28.2	
Spain	3.5	3.7	4.	3.	3.6	2.8	3.5	5.7	5.1	5.5

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 19 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: owner with mortgage or loan

Table 20 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: owner without mortgage or loan

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	21.1	20.6	20.5	19.8	19.4	18.4	18.1	18.1	17.6	16.6
Denmark	3.2	4.2	2.5	4.6	4.9	4.4	4.3	5.7	3.7	2.6
Italy	20.2	20.5	20.9	20.7	20.6	21.1	21.4	19.6	20.8	18.0
Latvia	35.9	37.6	38.2	40.6	38.8	39.0	38.9	38.8	37.9	37.8
Portugal	6.2	6.9	6.7	7.3	6.2	6.1	5.7	5.4	7.7	5.6
United Kingdom	1.6	1.5	1.0	1.3	0.9	1.2				
Serbia	51.7	48.0	51.3	53.3	54.1	50.9	51.0	50.6	49.1	
Turkey	50.3	50.9	50.0	47.8	47.1	45.8	43.7	42.4	41.3	
Spain	3.	3.5	3.9	4.	3.1	2.6	2.9	4.3	4.1	4.0

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

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Figure 20 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: owner without mortgage or loan

Table 21 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: tenant, rent at market value

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	19.8	20.4	20.5	21.2	21.2	21.6	21.9	23.1	23.9	23.4
Denmark	15.9	15.5	14.9	15.7	16.1	17.6	18.2	17.6	16.8	18.3
Italy	43.8	44.9	45.7	43.7	42.5	42.1	42.4	43.2	46.0	42.5
Latvia	57.6	61.6	63.3	63.9	64.6	65.9	57.0	66.6	60.0	65.2
Portugal	20.6	20.0	16.6	17.4	16.3	17.1	17.4	18.7	19.2	19.8
United Kingdom	16.2	14.6	16.1	14.1	5.4	9.6				
Serbia	80.1	72.5	74.7	79.8	80.6	79.7	80.5	74.1	73.6	
Turkey	39.8	43.1	42.1	41.5	39.9	38.6	37.3	37.1	36.7	
Spain	12.	12.	11.7	12.5	12.4	12.8	16.3	18.8	15.4	14.9

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 21 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: tenant, rent at market value

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Table 22 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: tenant, subsidised rent or free rent

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
European Union	27.0	27.1	26.4	26.4	25.1	25.1	26.2	28.0	25.5	25.1
Italy	38.7	39.0	36.8	36.4	34.7	36.2	38.4	36.2	38.5	34.1
Latvia	46.0	47.0	53.7	56.5	52.3	59.0	55.9	58.7	56.1	58.3
Portugal	21.4	18.4	19.2	17.6	17.1	17.7	17.6	12.7	15.3	14.9
United Kingdom	17.5	16.7	16.0	19.7	8.4	13.6				
Serbia	60.8	57.1	59.9	61.5	63.0	63.2	61.2	62.4	62.0	
Turkey	45.3	45.6	44.3	44.7	45.1	43.7	41.7	41.9	41.5	
Spain	11.7	10.8	10.1	10.9	9.	8.3	11.5	11.	6.9	9.8

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 22 - Overcrowding rate by tenure status: tenant, subsidised rent or free rent

Final consumption in households per capita

The table and graph below show the energy consumption in households per capita (this indicator measures how much electricity and heat every citizen consumes at home excluding energy used for transportation) in each partner country and at the European Union level over the last decade. These statistics show that the energy consumption in Portugal, Turkey and Spain is the lowest compared to the other partner countries.

Table 23 - Final energy consumption in households per capita

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
European Union	597	602	529	552	564	565	559	555	555	586
Denmark	795	799	735	782	801	781	769	755	735	772
Italy	577	568	486	535	531	543	528	521	516	542
Latvia	677	630	621	559	584	616	639	621	587	638
Portugal	256	252	267	266	273	272	280	281	293	292
United Kingdom	643	646	554	572	579	557	576	571		
Serbia	434	397	386	398	414	406	406	411	506	520
Turkey	269	260	248	258	261	276	253	261	276	314
Spain	332.	319.	318.	329.	308.	309.0	324.	306.	307.0	311.0

European Union (EU6-1958, EU9-1973, EU10-1981, EU12-1986, EU15-1995, EU25-2004, EU27-2007, EU28-2013, EU27-2020)

Figure 23 - Final energy consumption in households per capita

Main results from EUROSTAT data

In this statistical analysis, we observe the EUROSTAT data on the key variables that affects energy poverty in the EU and UK with a focus on the SUPERSHINE lighthouse countries (Denmark, Italy and Latvia), SUPERSHINE fellow countries (Serbia, Turkey, Portugal and Spain), SUPERSHINE partner country (United Kingdom) and the benchmark (European Union average level). Also, in this study we focus on the population with equivalised income below the 60% median, owners with outstanding mortgages or housing loans and tenants who pay subsidised rent or are rent free residents.

Lighthouse countries

Denmark

From the statistical analysis done by EUROSTAT on energy poverty measures in Denmark, the percentage of the population unable to keep their homes adequately warm during winter or cool during summer ranges between 6.6% and 10.9% across the period (2011-2022), which is the lowest compared to the other SUPERSHINE countries and the European Union. Also, we observe that the population in Denmark has the lowest rates of arrears on utility bills which is almost half that of the European Union. Also, the population in Denmark are less likely to suffer from poverty risk or social exclusion as shown in Table 6. In accordance with tables 2,4 and 6, tables 8 & 11 reports that owners with outstanding mortgage or housing loans and tenants that pay subsidised rent or are rent free residents in Denmark have a lower material and social deprivation rate compared to the EU Union countries. Table 13 reports that the percentage of low income households who live in poor condition dwellings suffering from leaking roofs, damp walls, floors, etc ranges between 14.9% and 16.8% which is fairly low compared to the other SUPERSHINE countries. Tables 15 and 18 show that the housing cost overburden rate ranges between 3.9 and 7.5 which is the lowest after the UK and Italy during the investigated period. Tables 19 and 22 show that the overcrowding rate ranges from 3.5% to 4.9% in Denmark and is the lowest compared to other SUPERSHINE countries after Spain. From table 23 we observe that the household final energy consumption is the highest in Denmark ranging from 735 to 801. Finally, we observe that energy poverty indicators in Denmark showed a slightly decreasing trend. However after 2020 we observe an increasing trend of the energy poverty indicators which can be explained by the sudden rise in inflation rate after the COVID-19 pandemic, which affected many households' income.

Italy

Tables 2 and 5 report that the percentage of people unable to keep their homes adequately warm in the winter and cool in the summer ranges between 17% and 44%. Furthermore, during the investigated period, we observe a significant decrease in this rate from 36.1% in 2011 to 17% in 2021. However, this decrease is not enough as the percentage of people in the European Union as a whole who are unable to keep their homes adequately warm is still lower. This statistic confirms the needs for Energy efficiency improvements in the current buildings in Italy. From table 4, we observe that the percentage of people with arrears on utility bills has been decreasing from 11.9% in 2013 to 4.5% in 2019, and increased to 6.5% in 2021, which can be explained by the impact of COVID-19 on the households ability to meet their financial needs and the rising inflation rate. In line with the previous findings, table 6 reports that the percentage of people at risk of poverty and social exclusion, even though decreasing, is high ranging from 24.6% to 28.5%. Tables 8 and 11 report the material and social deprivation rate in Italy for owners with mortgage and tenants who pay subsidised rent or are rent free. These tables show that the material and social deprivation rate is much higher than that of the European Union, even though its significantly decreasing throughout the investigated

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period. Table 13 reports that the percentage of low income people living in poor condition dwelling due to leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation has decreased from 30.1% in 2013 to 16.4% in 2019 and then rose back up to 24.5%. This sudden increase could be attributed to the increase in inflation rate and the impact of COVID-19 on the housing sector in Italy. Tables 19 and 22 show that social housing residents in Italy suffer from overcrowding issues as the overcrowding rate by owners with mortgages and tenants with subsidised rent is high and stable at 30% which is comparatively higher than that of the European union. Lastly, table 23 reports that the final energy consumption in households per capita in Italy is decreasing slightly from 577 in 2012 to 542 in 2022.

Latvia

Table 2 and 5 reports the percentage of people unable to keep their homes adequately warm in the winter and cool in the summer ranges between 12.4% and 40.8%. Like Italy, Latvia experienced a significant decrease in the percentage of people unable to keep their homes adequately warm in the winter or cool in the summer from 40.8% in 2011 to 12.4% in 2021 and then rose up to 18.3%. This sudden increase could be attributed to the impact of rising inflation rate in the EU. Table 4 shows that the percentage of arrears to utility bills is higher in Latvia compared to the European Union as a whole, even though during this period a significant decrease in arrears on utility bills is observed. In line with the findings of tables 2,4 and 5, table 6 reports that the share of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion in Latvia is the highest among the SUPERSHINE countries and the European Union countries. Table 13 reports that the percentage of low income people living in poor condition dwelling due to leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation has decreased from 44.1% in 2013 to 27.1% in 2020. Unlike in the case of Italy and Denmark, the low income people's status was not affected by the sudden increase in inflation rate and COVID-19 in the housing sector. Tables 15 and 18 report that the housing cost overburden rate of owners with mortgage and tenants paying subsidised rent has decreased from 16.2% in 2013 to 5.2% in 2022. However, even though Latvia has experienced a stable decrease in housing costs overburden rate, it is still high compared to the other SUPERSHINE countries except Serbia. Tables 19 and 22 show that social housing residents in Latvia suffer from overcrowding issues as the overcrowding rate by owners with mortgages and tenants with subsidised rent is high and increasing from 24.6%(46%) in 2013 to 37.2%(58.3%) in 2022 and is comparatively higher than that of the European union. Lastly, table 23 reports that the final energy consumption in households per capita in Latvia is decreasing slightly from 677 in 2012 to 638 in 2022.

Evaluation of existing financial schemes

As social housing is provided primarily to vulnerable and/or low-income households, it is typically not within the financial capacity of tenants to implement building improvements or equipment replacement, and it is therefore the responsibility of governments to develop effective building renovation measures. Further, studies suggest that government investment in improving social housing may be recouped through savings by national health systems.

Existing financial schemes

Denmark

The National Building Fund (LBF) is a cornerstone of the Danish affordable and social housing model, ensuring a high housing stock standard and better tenant well-being. It plays an important role in countercyclical efforts, such as the COVID-19 recovery stimulus. The LBF, established in 1967, is financed by tenant rents from the social and affordable housing provided by non-profit housing organisations. When mortgage loans for dwelling construction have been repaid, tenants pay rents at the same level, with the extra going into the LBF as a saving.

This fund finances the expansion of new affordable and social housing and renovation of existing properties. This includes improvements of both inside and outdoor areas, modernization of buildings to include access for elderly and disabled people, and energy improvements. The fund is also able to finance the demolition cost in vulnerable social housing areas, and to support infrastructural changes. LBF provides a useful mechanism to ensure self-financing in the social and affordable housing sector. Savings are recycled to help maintain and improve dwellings and provide additional housing. Therefore LBF provides a sealed finance circuit, reducing government need to reinvest in new social housing, and facilitates long-term planning for social housing funding. It also helps to even out variations in the financial strength of different social housing providers, in the costs of developing different estates, and thereby in rents charged which reflect development costs.

The purpose of the Fund¹⁶ is to build socially cohesive, safe, and sustainable communities. A particular focus is investments in social activities and rental price reductions. Efforts are organised in local partnerships such as schools, municipalities and Non-government organisations (NGOs), aiming to promote tenant employment opportunities and educational performance. The Fund is managed by a nine-member board, including representatives of housing organisations, tenants and the two largest municipalities in Denmark. However, its budget must be approved by the housing minister. The Danish government wants LBF to increase investments in energy-efficiency renovations, to play a key role in meeting climate goals and post-COVID-19 economic recovery.

Table 24 - : summary of available funding sources and needs - Denmark

Current Investment Needs for the period (2021-2030)	Currently available funding sources	
	At EU level	Country specific
1- EUR 1.615 billion (energy efficiency -Resilience and Recovery Plan)	EUR 808 million (EU Regional and Development Fund)	EUR 4.0 Bilion (National Building Fund)
2- EUR 4.0 billion (energy efficiency and renewable energy in district heating)	EUR 1.43 billion (NextGenerationEU)	EUR 143 milion (Denmark Government grants)
	Total : EUR 2.24 billion	Total : EUR 4.14 billion
Total investment needs: EUR 5.615 billion	Overall total of available investment sources: EUR 6.378 billion	

¹⁶ Kenneth Gibb, K, Duncan MacIennan and Mark Stephens, *Innovative Financing of Affordable Housing: international perspectives* (2013). Available at <https://www.jrf.org.uk/sites/default/files/jrf/migrated/files/affordable-housing-finance-full.pdf>.

Italy

As indicated by the report by **ENEA**¹⁷ (Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development) “Energy Efficiency trends and policies in ITALY”¹⁸. Social Houses in Italy can benefit from the following national measures incentivising energy retrofitting work:

- **Ecobonus**: a tax deduction of 110% of the expenses incurred for energy efficiency and seismic risk reduction in Italy. This measure was applicable for expenses incurred from 1st July 2020 until 31st December 2021 and the 110% deduction could be recovered in 5 annual instalments.
- **Conto Termico** [Thermal Energy Account] this is a non-repayable capital contribution granted for implementing small energy efficiency measures and producing thermal energy from renewable sources in existing air-conditioned public buildings registered with the Land Registry.
- **National Energy Efficiency Fund**¹⁹: this is an investment fund aiming to invest up to EUR 175m in energy efficiency (“EE”) projects and small/medium-scale renewable energy (“RE”) projects, mostly solar PV.

All over Italy, there are several success stories. For example, in Sicily, with the support of the Region and ENEA, the Municipality of Marsala (managed by the social housing company located in the city of Trapani) has implemented an energy efficiency programme for 80 social housing dwellings using **Public-Private Partnerships**. This EE programme has the goal to upgrade the heating and hot water systems while improving the building insulation and installing solar PVs. The project has been developed in line with the Minimum Requirements Decree: it is expected to generate energy savings of around 80% compared to the existing situation, allowing the building to achieve nZEB classification. The planned interventions are eligible for the *Conto Termico* incentive scheme.

Table 25 - summary of available funding sources and needs - Italy

Current Investment Needs for the period (2021-2030)	Currently available funding sources	
	At EU level	Country specific
1- EUR 15.3 billion (energy efficiency in public buildings)	EUR 8.7 billion (EU Regional and Development Fund)	EUR 175 million (Italian Energy Efficiency Fund) EUR 310 million (Invitalia)
2- EUR 11.2 billion (energy efficiency and renewable energy in district heating and waste and water management)	EUR 24.9 billion (NextGenerationEU)	EUR 47 million (Emilia-Romagna Energy Fund)
	Total : EUR 33.6 billion	Total : EUR 532 million
Total investment needs: EUR 26.5 billion	Overall total of available investment sources: EUR 34.13 billion	

Latvia

According to the National Energy and Climate Plan NECP (2021) of Latvia, the primary sources for financing the 2030 objectives are the national and municipal budgets, financial support from the European Union funds, proceeds generated from the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), and contributions from private investments. According to the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) for the period of 2021-2030, projections indicate that the expenses required to meet climate objectives will constitute around 0.35% of the nation's yearly gross domestic product (GDP). This deliverable presents an overview of the existing funding schemes that are currently accessible for energy-efficient renovations in the context of social housing.

¹⁷ <https://www.enea.it/en/enea/about-us>

¹⁸ Iorio, G. and Federici, A. (2021). Energy efficiency trends and policies in Italy. <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/national-reports/energy-efficiency-italy.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://www.cib.org/en/registers/all/127000349>

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- **Selling Emission Allowances²⁰**: Latvia is projected to auction around 16 million EU emission allowances throughout the period spanning from 2021 to 2030. The implementation of an emission trading system has the potential to generate a revenue range of EUR 500 to 750 million, which is contingent upon several factors, including the price of European emission allowances. According to the findings of Kamenders et al. (2020), it was determined that over 60% of the revenues generated from the auctions were designated for the purpose of funding energy efficiency and renewable energy initiatives, amounting to a total of EUR 375 million.
- **Modernization Fund²¹**: is financed by the proceeds generated by the auctioning of 2% of the overall allowances allocated for the period spanning from 2021 to 2030. The allocation of the Modernization Fund is intended to provide financial support for initiatives aimed at enhancing energy efficiency and modernising the energy sector in ten lower-income Member States of the European Union, including Latvia. Given the price range of EUR 25M to 30.5M per permit, and considering that about 1.44% of the resources were allocated to Latvia.²²
- **Next Generation EU²³**: is the most substantial fund under the European Union's Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) with the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) for the period of 2021-2027. Latvia is allocated a fixed amount of EUR 1.65 billion in the form of grants, while an additional variable amount of EUR 0.37 billion is predicted. The expected maximum budget allocated to Latvia amounts to EUR 2.02 billion. With a climate share of 37%, Latvia has the potential to access around EUR 747 million in grants and loans for investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy. In order to gain access to the aforementioned resources, it is necessary for the Ministry of Finance, in collaboration with the Cross-sectoral Coordination Centre, to formulate a comprehensive Recovery & Resilience Plan and thereafter submit it to the European Commission for approval.
- **European Regional Development Fund**: holds the distinction of being the second largest budgetary allocation within the European Union. Notably, it possesses a significant climate share of 30%. According to Kamenders et al. (2020), preliminary projections indicate that EU Cohesion policy allocations within the next EU multiannual financial framework would contribute an estimated EUR 464 million towards energy efficiency and renewable energy initiatives in Latvia.
- **ALTUM and EIB loans**: the European Investment Bank (EIB) has just entered into a loan agreement with ALTUM, the national promotional organisation of Latvia, for a total amount of EUR 18 million. This loan is specifically aimed at providing financial support to Latvian enterprises engaged in energy efficiency initiatives. The finance is supplemented by a guarantee of EUR 3 million through the "Private Finance for Energy Efficiency" mechanism, which is funded by the European Union under the LIFE initiative (L'Instrument Financier pour l'Environnement).²⁴.
The table below summarises the investment needs in energy efficiency and renewable energy projects and the financial sources available for them. From this table we observe a significant gap of EUR 2.25 billion that is necessary to meet the Latvia NECP 2021-2030 objectives.

²⁰ Latvia's eight national communication(2022), https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/78450136_Latvia-NC8-BR5-2-LATVIA_NC8_BR5_Resubmission.pdf

²¹ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/funding-climate-action/modernisation-fund_en

²² Information Report on the Implementation of the Modernization Fund <http://tap.mk.gov.lv/mk/tap/?pid=40476379>

²³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/health/coronavirus-response/recovery-plan-europe_en#documents

²⁴ <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2020-074-altum-and-eib-join-forces-for-energy-efficiency-investments-in-latvia>

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Table 26 - summary of available funding sources and needs - Latvia

Current Investment Needs for the period (2021-2030)	Currently available funding sources	
	At EU level	Country specific
1- EUR 1.73 billion (energy efficiency in buildings)	EUR 60 million (Modernization fund) EUR 224 million (Next generation EU)	EUR 375 million (Emission selling) EUR 18 million (ALTUMloans)
2- EUR 1.66 billion (energy efficiency and renewable energy in district heating)	EUR 839 million (European regional development fund) EUR 192 million (Just Transition Fund) EUR 1.2 billion (EU social fund plus) EUR 1.2 billion (EU Cohesion fund)	
	Total : EUR 3.715 billion	Total : EUR 393 million
Total investment needs: EUR 3.39 billion	Overall total of available investment sources: EUR 4.11 billion	

Innovative business models and financial schemes

According to the *European Portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings*²⁵, to accelerate the implementation of EE in social housing in the EU innovative financial schemes such as Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), Energy Performance Contracting (EPC), Crowdfunding (CF) and Green Loans are required. Regarding PPPs, the European Court of Auditors (ESA) has published an overview of the state of the art and application of PPPs in the EU.

As improvement of EE has become a priority of governments, the public sector has become increasingly aware of the specific barriers related to development, financing, and implementation of EE projects²⁶. Many EE projects have negative costs over the lifetime of the project, but the government may not have the ability to invest and tie up large amounts of public funding for projects with long pay-back profiles. The partnering of the government with local financial institutions (LFIs) and energy services companies (ESCOs) enable PPPs to deliver market-oriented instruments that target specific EE market barriers, without the need for direct government subsidy programmes. It also allows governments to achieve their EE targets with only a fraction of the public funding that would otherwise be required, with the private sector taking on both the financial and performance risks.

Moreover, while a lot of attention has been focused on fiscal leveraging of projects, governments often look to the private sector to help them deliver infrastructure for several other reasons as a way of:

- **introducing private sector technology and innovation** in order to provide better public services through improved operational efficiency.
- gradually exposing governments and state-owned enterprises to **increasing levels of private sector participation** and structuring PPPs in a way to ensure transfer of skills.
- extracting long-term value-for-money through appropriate **risk transfer to the private sector** over the life of a project, from its design and construction to its operations and maintenance.
- **developing local private sector capabilities** through joint ownership with large international firms.
- creating diversification in the economy *by making the country more competitive* by facilitating its infrastructure base as well as boosting its business and industry associated with infrastructure development.
- **reducing energy intensity** of the economy at a faster pace.
- **allowing greater commercial value** for the public sector.

The partnering of the government with local financial institutions (LFIs) and energy services companies (*ESCOs*) enables the structuring of PPPs to deliver market-oriented instruments that target specific EE market barriers, without the need for direct government subsidy programmes.

²⁵Energy-efficient Buildings contractual Public-Private Partnership: 2018 Progress Monitoring Report
<https://www.buildup.eu/en/practices/publications/energy-efficient-buildings-contractual-public-private-partnership-2018>

²⁶ Singh, J., D. R. Limaye, B. Henderson, and X. Shi (2010), Public Procurement of Energy Efficiency Services, Washington DC: the World Bank

Description of the SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Surveys

The main objective of the SUPER-i SUPERSHINE surveys (**SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey for LIGHTHOUSES buildings** and **SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey Lighthouse districts**) are the collection of available qualitative and quantitative data on the building and district levels specific to each LIGHTHOUSE country (Latvia, Italy and Denmark) necessary to perform a comprehensive financial evaluation analysis, Life cycle analysis, analyse the current need for the energy efficiency refurbishments, and analyse the current socio-economic situation of the residents. The two SUPERSHINE surveys consisted of 89 questions related to information on the building level, and 49 questions related to information on the district level. These questions were developed in collaboration with the SUPERSHINE partners and building upon the knowledge gathered from the **SUPER-i project**. The *SUPER-i SUPERSHINE survey for LIGHTHOUSES building (Annex 1)* and *SUPER-i SUPERSHINE survey for LIGHTHOUSES district (Annex 2)* questions are organised into 5 main sections which are:

- General information about the buildings
- Technical information about the construction materials and current condition of walls, roofs, windows and floors.
- Financial and socio-economic
- Environmental
- Social

Lastly, the SUPER-i SUPERSHINE surveys were circulated among the SUPERSHINE Lighthouses and Fellows to collect an initial dataset which is in the process of being analysed and which will be updated during the duration of the project.

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey for LIGHTHOUSES

Denmark

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey building

Figure 24 - Department 16 with totally 5 building blocks with similar construction etc. (grey roof)

General:

The **FællesBo Department 16** in **Herning** neighbourhood consists of 5 building blocks, with a total of 89 apartments (18 per building) of average size 74 m², owned by **FællesBo Social Housing Company**. The buildings were constructed in 1958, and were renovated twice in 1984 and 1996. The population density is 160 tenants in total and 1 resident per 41 m². These buildings do not have a building passport or environmental declaration certificate.

The **FællesBo Department 16** buildings have a central heating and hot water systems, individual ventilation system, and LED lightings. Currently, the buildings do not have any renewable energy sources.

Technical:

The current installed energy systems allows the residents to control the internal temperature of the dwellings, able to open the windows to improve air quality inside the dwellings, but are not able to control the humidity within the dwellings. The current central heating ensures that the temperature during winter does not fall below 21°C. The initial energy performance certificate of the building was **category D**, and after renovations the energy certificate is **category C** with average annual energy consumption of **147 kWh/m²** per annum. This average per building is expected to fall to **78 kWh/m²** per annum after the proposed interventions for energy efficiency refurbishment are completed. The proposed interventions include:

- **Envelope:** Replacement of roof, re-insulation of attic space, New shell wall and subsequent insulation of the facade, the basement stairs are replaced in connection with the facade renovation, New windows and doors in the facade (incl. basement), Floor deck insulation above basement incl. ceiling formwork, Mailbox system and door phone, Painting of stairwells, Renovation of the basement, including installations (Not new heating installations –the existing ones have a long life), Sewage separation, New spacious bathroom with underfloor heating, Floor heating system, Preparation for

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wash column in bathroom, New open kitchen/possibility of screened kitchen some places, Sound insulation vertically and horizontally, New entrance door, New wooden floors and baseboards, New interior doors, New electrical installations, New balanced ventilation, New plumbing installations, and new extended balcony/terrace where possible.

- **Systems:** Maintaining biomass cogeneration district heating for heating and DHW.
- **Renewable energy sources:** Rooftop PV system for the departments' common electricity consumption (lighting on common areas, washing machines), and Rooftop PV systems for electricity supply to the tenants having individual electricity supply for each flat.

Financial and socio-economic:

The table below shows the amount of investment required to cover the planned EE renovations and the expected energy savings for each installed EE technology with an average life cycle between 20 years and 30 years depending on the EE technology.

Table 27 - investment cost for EE technologies and expected energy savings per year

Measure	Investment EUR	Savings kWh/year
Electricity		
New LED lighting common areas (electricity)	28,993	32,000
PV (electricity)	130,470	33,000
Heating		
Thermostat	25,101	58,000
Insulation of division between floors towards cellar	83,356	41,000
New 3-layer low energy windows, 0,87 W/m ² K	55,570	34,000
Heating pipe insulation	22,416	14,000
Wall cavity insulation	20,537	8,000
New doors-facades in balconies and at entrance	731,544	277,000
Insulation of roof (400 mm rockwool granulate)	49,369	13,000
DHW pipe insulation	26,846	6,000
Totally, heating	1,174,201	516,000
Heating savings: 69 kWh/m ² /year.		451,000

In general the housing association is financed via capital loans from the municipality of 8-12% of the building costs, residents' deposit 2% of the building costs and mortgage loans with a maximum 40 years of depreciation with municipal guarantee covering 86-90% of the building costs. Resident deposits can be equated with equity. The resident's deposit is now 100,00 EUR. When the mortgage loan is repaid (unamortized), the department pays a sum into the Landsbyggefonden and a sum into the housing organisation's disposal fund (which is a common fund for all housing departments in a housing organisation). Currently before the EE renovation in the buildings, the residents in **FaellesBo Department 16** consume **147 kWh/m²** a year in Heat consumption, at a price of **5545 DKK/kWh** a year. This is equivalent to **937 DKK/year per household**. The residents in **FaellesBo Department 16** are divided into 3 groups based on wage band and number of family members, on average a single person household on social welfare makes around 25,000 EUR/year, a 2 person household with 1 person working make around 40,000 EUR/year, and 2 person household both working make around 70,000 EUR/year. Thus, the percentage of cost of heat consumption per year to the annual income per household ranges between 1.5% to 4% depending on the wage band of the household. The residents in **FaellesBo Department 16** consume on average 2000 kWh/year in electricity.

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Thus, the percentage of cost of electricity consumption per year to the annual income per household ranges between 1.8% to 5.2% depending on the wage band of the household. Furthermore, **FællesBo social housing company** estimates that 20% of their managed households are not able to keep their homes adequately warm. Lastly, during the energy efficiency renovations period the current inhabitants will be allocated to other social houses in close proximity to FaellesBo district.

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey District

The **FællesBo District** is located in south-western part of Herning town. The district consists of 4 FællesBo departments of mixed areas with a population density of 51,000 residents on 1324 km² (39 inhabitants per km²). The inhabitants of the **FællesBo District** have access to several public services such as Schools, medical offices, shopping mall, public transport, green areas, bicycle paths, leisure centres, culture and art centres, industrial park, libraries and centres for elderly and children. The planned energy efficiency renovations will install PV systems on the roofs of the residential housing blocks, and charging stations will be established on existing parking areas. Furthermore, Neogrid smart energy management technology is being installed for the purpose of optimising energy savings and indoor comfort (currently in the testing period). The public infrastructure used in the **FællesBo District** consists of district heating, electricity grid, fibre cable grid, public lighting system, and domestic water supply network. The key stakeholders involved in the energy efficiency renovation process are FaellesBo social housing company, tenants of FaellesBo district, local building renovation expert companies, the municipality, landsbyggefonden funding institution, and local ESCOs carrying out the renewable energy sources renovations. The planned energy efficiency refurbishment in the FaellesBo district is intended to increase energy efficiency of the public lighting system, energy efficiency of the water network, installing renewable energy systems such as the FællesBo PV systems, and improving the mobility system such as establishing EV charging stations. Furthermore, FaellesBo social housing is teaming up with local business and ESCOs to develop a **crowdfunding scheme** for financing the installation of the planned energy efficiency renovations.

The table below specifies main characteristics of the social housing inhabitants within the FaellesBo district.

Table 28 - Summary of inhabitants characteristics - FaellesBo district

Age group	74% below 60 years old
	26% over 60 years old
Employment rate	70% are employed
Education	50% without proper education
Wage band	Single person household on social welfare around 25,000 EUR/year
	single person households working lower middle class around 40,000 EUR/year
	2 persons household both working 70-80,000 EUR/year.
Ethnicity	80% are Danish
	20% are emigrants
Relationship status	60% single
	31% families/couples
	9% single parents

Social engagement

The **Fællesbo district** in Herning, specifically **Department 16**, includes five building blocks with 89 apartments and 160 residents. Constructed in 1958 and previously renovated in 1984 and 1996, the district currently holds an energy performance rating of C with an annual energy consumption of 147 kWh/m². Planned renovations are expected to reduce this figure to 78 kWh/m² through comprehensive measures such as insulation upgrades, new ventilation systems, and rooftop photovoltaic (PV) installations for communal and individual electricity supply. These energy efficiency improvements aim to enhance living conditions, reduce energy costs, and address energy poverty. Social engagement in Fællesbo is facilitated by established community structures, including resident boards and activity committees, which play an active role in fostering communication and participation among tenants. Informal activities, such as "Bingo" nights, have proven effective in building connections and encouraging resident involvement. However, significant cultural and social barriers remain. The district's population is predominantly Danish, with 20% belonging to ethnic minority groups. These residents often face language barriers that limit their ability to access information and participate in community initiatives fully. Additionally, cultural differences in expectations and communication styles can hinder their engagement with energy efficiency programs. The socio-economic profile of Fællesbo residents highlights further challenges. Households are divided into three primary wage bands: single-person households on social welfare earning approximately €25,000 annually, two-person households with one income earning €40,000 annually, and two-person households with dual incomes earning €70,000 annually. Heating costs account for 1.5–4% of household income, while electricity costs represent 1.8–5.2%. Although these expenses are manageable for most, approximately 20% of households report difficulty maintaining adequate warmth during winter. This issue is particularly pronounced among lower-income and minority households, exacerbating energy poverty and creating disparities in comfort levels. Cultural challenges also emerge in decision-making and participation. Civic engagement is dominated by older residents, who are more familiar with traditional processes and routines. This generational divide often deters younger residents from participating, as they feel their perspectives are underrepresented or overlooked. Furthermore, resistance to change among older tenants, who are less willing to adapt to new technologies or disruptions caused by renovations, poses a significant barrier to social engagement. Temporary relocations during the renovation process further exacerbate these challenges, particularly for vulnerable groups who may feel displaced and unsettled. To address these cultural and social barriers, transparent and inclusive communication strategies are essential. Providing clear, consistent updates on renovation timelines, benefits, and measures to minimize disruptions can help build trust and support among tenants. For example, emphasizing the nearly 50% reduction in energy consumption and the long-term cost savings expected from the renovations can make the benefits more tangible. The planned introduction of **Neogrid smart energy management technology** presents an opportunity to engage residents by empowering them to monitor and optimize their energy usage. However, this initiative will require culturally sensitive training programs to ensure accessibility for all tenants, including those with limited language proficiency or technical skills. Collaboration with local stakeholders, such as ESCOs, SMEs, and community leaders, is also critical for fostering engagement. These partnerships can help co-design district activities and create opportunities for broader community involvement. Cultural inclusion must remain a priority, with efforts to address language barriers, provide multilingual resources, and engage minority groups in decision-making processes. By building on existing community structures and addressing these cultural challenges, the Fællesbo district can achieve a more inclusive and engaged community, ensuring the success of its energy efficiency initiatives.

Italy

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey for buildings:

The **Boito** neighbourhood consists of 8 building blocks, with a total of 128 apartments (16 per building) of average 2.5 inhabitant per dwelling at the moment and 3.5 inhabitant per dwelling after rebuilding, owned by **ATER Trieste**. The buildings were constructed in 1951, and have not been renovated since. These buildings do not have a building passport or environmental declaration certificate. The **Boito** buildings do not have a central heating and hot water systems, individual ventilation system, and LED lighting. Currently, the buildings do not have any renewable energy sources and are set to be demolished and rebuilt using the latest energy efficiency technologies. Furthermore, after the construction of the new buildings, the expected energy performance rating of each building is A2. The expected cost for the demolition and construction of the 8 buildings in Boito is 16,500,000.00 EUR which is paid in equal instalments of 25% over the next 4 years. After the reconstruction, the buildings will not be put for private ownership and will be allocated to low income households with the same subsidised rent. Furthermore, the current households spend on average 6,400 EUR per year on energy consumption which equates to 40% of their annual salary. Also, 60% or households in Italy cannot afford to keep their homes adequately warm during winter and cool during summer which is in line with the EUROSTAT statistics.

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey for districts:

The residents in **Boito district** have access to public services such as schools, medical offices, shops, public transport services, green areas, leisure centres, industrial parks, centres for children, and the municipality of Trieste is currently planning the addition of bicycle paths and centres for elderly. Furthermore, there are no extra lands available for future developments excluding the land intended for the municipality master plan (generic), the lands available for ATER projects and current building restorations. Currently, the Boito district does not have a central district heating system, energy production system or renewable energy production systems. The planned energy efficiency renovation in the new buildings in Boito district are focused on improving the energy efficiency in public buildings, public lighting systems, mobility systems, creating smart city/community projects, installing heat and power cogeneration systems and renewable energy systems. The involved stakeholders in the energy efficiency renovations are: Municipality of Trieste, FVG region and public utilities providers. The energy efficiency renovations planned for the district will be funded using regional and state funds. At the moment, all the buildings in Boito district are vacant (set for demolition), and will be rented to low income inhabitants after the construction of the new buildings.

Table 29 - Summary of inhabitants characteristics - Boito district

Age group	13% of the inhabitants are 0-17 years old
	30% of the inhabitants are 17-49 years old
	57% of the inhabitants are 50+ years old
Employment rate	Not available
Education	Not available
Wage band	59%, Salary < EUR 10,000
	38%, EUR 10,000 < Salary < EUR 20,000
	3%, EUR 20,000 < Salary < EUR 30,000
Ethnicity	87% are Italian
	2% are from the EU
	11% are not from Non-EU

Social engagement

The **Boito district** in Trieste consists of eight building blocks with a total of 128 apartments, all of which are currently vacant. Constructed in 1951, these buildings have not undergone any renovations since their construction and are now set for demolition and reconstruction. The redevelopment plan includes modern, energy-efficient buildings expected to achieve an A2 energy performance rating. These new homes will cater to low-income households and will maintain subsidized rents, ensuring affordability. However, the energy poverty situation in Italy poses significant challenges, as households in Boito are estimated to spend an average of €6,400 annually on energy bills, equating to 40% of their income. This aligns with national statistics indicating that 60% of Italian households cannot afford to maintain adequate heating or cooling, reflecting a critical need for intervention. Cultural challenges in Boito significantly affect social engagement. Residents, many of whom earn less than €10,000 per year (59%), often mistrust authorities and perceive energy renovations as imposed measures that disregard their preferences and disrupt their lives. This mistrust is further compounded by scepticism about the benefits of energy efficiency programs, with many residents fearing increased costs and insufficient returns on investment. These beliefs are deeply rooted in a historical lack of transparency in public housing projects, creating barriers to engagement and participation. The demographic profile of the future Boito residents, who will predominantly consist of economically disadvantaged groups, underscores the need for targeted engagement strategies. These households often prioritize immediate comfort and family well-being over long-term sustainability, reflecting cultural values that emphasize short-term needs over broader environmental goals. Additionally, the absence of existing renewable energy systems, such as central district heating, limits the residents' exposure to energy-efficient practices, further challenging their willingness to adopt new technologies. To overcome these barriers, a multi-faceted approach to social engagement is necessary. Community meetings and workshops, supported by local stakeholders such as the Municipality of Trieste and ATER Trieste, can serve as platforms for educating residents about the benefits of energy efficiency. Multilingual materials and visual guides will be essential in ensuring accessibility for all. Furthermore, involving residents in co-designing public spaces and energy-saving measures will foster a sense of ownership and trust. Addressing cultural concerns directly, such as fears of cost increases and disruptions, will require transparent communication about the long-term financial and comfort benefits of these renovations. By prioritizing these efforts, the Boito district can create a more engaged and informed community, ensuring the success of its redevelopment plan.

Latvia

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey for buildings

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General:

The **Hruschovka** neighbourhood consists of 316 series multi-apartment buildings constructed in 1960. The Hruschovka buildings are constructed in two sizes - 4 to 6 staircases where each staircase has access to 10 apartments of different dimensions (*Single room apartment, two rooms apartment, and three rooms apartment*). The number of apartments per building is 51 apartments on average with population density 2.3 person per apartment. These apartments are privately owned and managed by the **Rigas namu parvaldnieks** in partnership with the **municipal housing management**.

Technical:

The **Hruschovka** buildings have a central heating and hot water systems using gas and biomass as energy sources. The current installed energy systems do not allow the residents to control the internal temperature and humidity of the dwellings. The current central heating ensures that the temperature during winter does not fall below 16°C. The energy performance certificate rating per building ranges between **F** and **E** with average annual energy consumption of **223 kWh/m²** per annum. This average per building is expected to fall by **133 kWh/m²** per annum after the proposed interventions for energy efficiency refurbishment are completed. The proposed interventions include:

- **Envelope:** Insulation of external walls, insulation of attic floor, insulation of foundations, insulation of cellar's roof, PVC window installation, replacement of external doors.
- **Systems:** Renovation of heating system (incl. possibility for individual temp. regulation), insulation and replacement of hot water system and tubes, renovation of ventilation system.
- **Renewable energy sources:** Rooftop PV is currently possible for communal energy use only due to lack of Energy community regulation in Latvia. Depending on the final date of renovation, PV panels may be installed for communal use only, or, if Energy community laws are passed by then, for individual use also.
- **Candidate changes to the building:** Potential exterior and interior cosmetic repairs.

Financial and socio-economic:

Currently, there are several funding sources available to energy efficiency refurbishments in Latvia such as the National & EU Grants, investment from local financial institutions and private savings from the owning entity to co-finance the proposed energy efficiency refurbishments in **Hruschovka**. After the implementation of the EE refurbishment the market value of the buildings is expected to increase by 40%. However, the estimated cost for implementing the proposed energy efficiency refurbishments has risen from **127 EUR/m²** to **400 EUR/m²** Due to the unavailability of basic building materials and the current global energy crisis.

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey for districts:

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The Sustainable Development Programme of Riga 2021-2027 has marked **Agenskalna priedes** as the renovation wave pilot area. The **Agenskalna priedes** district serves as a residential function with services at its periphery such as schools, Medical offices, Shops, Public transport, Green areas, Leisure centres, Culture and art centres. The land of the **Agenskalna priedes** is owned by the municipality, and part of the vacant lands and buildings rooftops are put available for the installation of renewable energy generations and storage solutions. All the buildings in the **Agenskalna priedes** district are connected by centralised district heating and domestic hot water systems, supplying the area with cogeneration thermal energy. The public infrastructure used in the **Agenskalna priedes** district consist of a public lighting system, newly installed public underground waste sorting facility, water and sewerage network and newly installed playground for the children. The key stakeholders involved in the energy efficiency renovation process are: residents of the district, house managers, municipal housing maintenance company, and the Riga Municipal Agency to provide technical support in the implementation of the EE refurbishments. Also, the **Agenskalna priedes** consists of mixed public and private ownership of the land, which is acting as a barrier to possible investments by the municipality in district development initiatives and has caused delays up to 2 years for the adoption of the EE refurbishment in the district.

Currently, there is no collaboration with the local business to uptake new technologies targeting social and affordable housing. However, since the launch of the SUPERSHINE project, the residents of the Agenskalna priedes district are planning to establish an NGO for the district. Also the Riga City Municipality offers several municipal grants to support small-scale community projects for improving public spaces. Furthermore, the Riga municipality is developing with collaboration from local ESCO's, housing maintenance companies and Riga city residents a large scale fund "**Riga Energy Efficiency Fund**" to accelerate energy renovations of multi apartment residential buildings in the Riga city. Also, a municipal ESCO service provider is currently managing 23 residential buildings in the district and providing households with various property and infrastructure management services such as building management, cleaning of the staircases and outdoor areas, organising of the waste management services, and emergency repair services.

Table 30 - Summary of inhabitants characteristics - Agenskalna priedes (Explicit reference to EUROSTAT data)

Age group	Average age of residents 43 years
Employment rate	4.3% are unemployed in the Riga city
	2.0% are unemployed in the Agenskalna priedes district
Education	Not available
Wage band	Above the average of the Riga city: EUR 15,600 per year
Ethnicity	Latvian, Russian, Ukrainian, Belarussian, Polish, Jewish, and Lithuanian

Social Engagement

The **Agenskalna Priedes district** in Riga, a pilot area under the Riga Sustainable Development Programme 2021–2027, consists of Soviet-era Hruschovka buildings constructed in the 1960s. These multi-apartment buildings, with an average energy performance rating of F to E, house a diverse population, including Latvian, Russian, Ukrainian, and other ethnic groups. Residents face significant challenges related to energy poverty and engagement with energy efficiency programs. Planned renovations aim to reduce annual energy consumption from 223 kWh/m² to 133 kWh/m² through envelope insulation, heating system upgrades, and rooftop photovoltaic (PV) installations for communal use. However, a combination of financial, cultural, and structural barriers impacts social engagement and the success of these projects.

Residents' Needs

Financial challenges are a key concern for the district. Approximately 5% of residents are in arrears on their energy bills, with the most vulnerable groups being elderly and low-income households. These groups often overlap, particularly in areas with a historically impoverished background. While national and EU grants are accessible to all residents, those at risk of energy poverty show lower interest in utilizing these funds. This reluctance stems from both a lack of awareness and skepticism about the benefits of energy efficiency measures. In terms of comfort and well-being, the centralized heating system ensures a minimum indoor temperature of 16°C during winter, leaving residents with little control over individual heating preferences. While this prevents severe cold exposure, it limits opportunities for cost-saving adjustments. Cooling needs in Latvia are minimal, and most residents rely on natural ventilation rather than mechanical cooling systems. However, cold spots in poorly insulated buildings can lead to health issues, and high energy bills contribute to stress among low-income residents. Housing conditions exacerbate energy poverty, with poor insulation being the primary issue. The Hruschovka buildings were constructed during a time when heat was a byproduct of industrial processes, resulting in minimal attention to the insulative properties of the building envelope. This legacy has left many buildings highly inefficient and costly to heat.

Cultural Barriers

The heritage of Soviet-era governance poses a significant cultural barrier to engagement. During this period, residents had little responsibility for property upkeep, as maintenance was managed by state entities. This legacy has led to a persistent lack of self-responsibility among residents regarding their buildings, which impacts participation in energy efficiency projects. Many residents remain skeptical of government-led initiatives, with older generations expressing particular distrust of authorities. This skepticism extends to Riga's municipal housing management company, which some view as ineffective or self-serving. Residents also exhibit fears about financial impacts, particularly concerns that the costs of renovations may not yield sufficient energy savings to justify the investment. While there is no fear of rent increases (as the target audience comprises apartment owners), doubts persist about whether savings will cover the costs of renovations. This skepticism is partly rooted in poor experiences with earlier renovation projects, which were not well-executed, leading to issues such as mold growth post-insulation. Misconceptions about building physics further fuel resistance, with some residents questioning the necessity of insulating thick brick walls.

Beliefs, Perceptions, and Values

Residents' beliefs about energy efficiency projects reflect both cultural and practical concerns. While all apartment owners have a voice in decision-making, some perceive that renovations may be imposed on them without adequate consent. This perception can lead to resistance, even if it is not supported by the actual participatory structure in place. Additionally, while relocation is not required during renovations, residents may still view the process as disruptive to their routines, creating further reluctance. In terms of perceptions, about half of the residents view energy-efficient renovations as an improvement in quality of life, while the other half see them as unnecessary disruptions. Concerns about costs and fears of mold formation post-insulation contribute to this split. Residents also value the aesthetics of their buildings, and any proposed changes to the exterior design must consider this priority. When it comes to values, immediate financial benefits and comfort take precedence over long-term environmental goals. Residents think of environmental sustainability primarily in terms of the functionality of shared outdoor spaces rather than energy savings. This focus on communal well-being reflects a cultural value tied to the use of shared spaces, yet it does not always translate into support for energy upgrades within private buildings.

Norms and Expectations

The norms of communal living in Āgenskalna Priedes have been shaped by decades of centralized control. Ventilation habits, such as keeping windows open year-round, conflict with modern energy-saving systems like recuperative ventilation. Despite this, such systems are rarely installed due to high costs. Civic

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participation in Latvia remains low overall, and residents’ responses to government-led initiatives are mixed. Older generations tend to be skeptical, while younger residents are more opportunistic, showing interest when funding opportunities arise. Residents’ expectations for energy efficiency programs revolve around comfort, cost savings, and the long-term safety of their buildings. However, the payback period for renovations, often exceeding 20 years, dampens enthusiasm. Subsidy schemes that reduce payback times to around 20 years are considered more acceptable. Additionally, due to widespread distrust, some residents expect to be closely involved in monitoring and overseeing renovation work to ensure its proper implementation.

Inclusivity and Accessibility

Language and cultural diversity pose significant challenges to inclusivity in Āgenskalna Priedes. While the quarter itself is relatively homogenous, with many Latvian-speaking residents, non-native speakers, particularly those in the Russian-speaking community, face difficulties accessing information. The phasing out of Russian as a public communication language further complicates engagement for these residents. Elderly residents, who may lack digital skills, also struggle to access online resources, limiting their ability to participate in discussions and decision-making processes. Efforts to enhance accessibility have included multilingual community meetings and forums with workshop elements. These events have proven effective, though their success depends heavily on marketing and promotion. The Riga Energy Agency’s One-Stop-Shop (OSS) has played a pivotal role in bridging these gaps, offering personalized support and attending community meetings to provide information and guidance. However, more consistent use of alternative communication formats, such as visual guides and multilingual materials, is needed to fully engage all residents.

SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Survey for FELLOW districts

Portugal

The population density in **Setubal district** is 534.6 inhabitants per m2. The residents in **Setubal district** have access to several public services such as schools, medical offices, shops, public transport services, green areas, bicycle paths, pedestrian areas, leisure centres, culture and art centres, industrial parks, centres for elderly and children and libraries. Also, the municipality of Setubal is planning marina services to support the nautical activities in the River Sado. According to the Municipality of Setubal, there is land available for new buildings and infrastructure, and plans to use building roofs to install new renewable energy production systems across the district. The **Setubal** has 8 solare energy production systems namely Bacalhõa (Azeitão); José Maria da Fonseca; Pavilhão Antoine Velge; Delta Cafés (Setúbal); Centro Hospitalar de Setúbal; Photovoltaic Plant of Algeruz II; and The Navigator Company (Setúbal) – Expansão which owns the largest Biomass plant in the region. However, the district does not have central district heating systems. Furthermore, the current infrastructure includes a public lighting system with over 35,000 light points which are made up of LED and Sodium lamps and a water network with 20 groundwater abstractions, 726 km of distribution network, 8 pumping stations and 18 reservoirs. The involved local stakeholders in the energy efficiency renovations are: the city council, ENA, and local industries. Also, note that there is a lack of local and private investments in the district. The planned energy efficiency renovations are intended to increase the energy efficiency in public buildings and public lighting systems, creating smart city projects and energy communities, Setting up shared energy production systems between buildings, and installing renewable energy systems and mobility systems. Currently, the public authorities offer financial support in terms of grants to energy efficiency renovation in social housing level.

Table 31 - Summary of inhabitants social characteristics - Setubal

Age group	14.00% 0-14 years old
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	43.00% 15-49 years old
	43.00% 50+ years old
Employment rate	9.12% are unemployed
Education	5% no education
	17% primary education
	28% Basic education
	27% Secondary education
	21% University level
Wage band	EUR 929.22 per month: Uneducated
	EUR 1050 per month: Primary education
	EUR 1090.21 per month: Basic education
	EUR 1169.32 per month: Secondary education
	EUR 1943.13 per month : Bachelor degree
	EUR 1983.76 per month: Masters degree
	EUR 2496.95 per month: Doctoral
Ethnicity	Not available

Spain

The Population density in **Actur Rey Fernando** in Zaragoza city is 6 habitants per m2. The inhabitants have access to several public services such as schools, medical offices, shops, public transport services, green areas, bicycle paths, pedestrian areas, leisure centres, culture and art centres, centres of elderly and children, and libraries. **Actur Rey Fernando district** has a central district heating system with biomass and experience with solar energy systems in the solar district. The local stakeholders involved in the planned energy efficiency renovations are: municipal housing, city hall, communities of neighbours and neighbours associations. Currently, there is funding provided to several running projects in the district such as **Neutralpath** project to improve energy efficiency in public buildings and **Barrio solar** to create self-consumption community. The **Actur Rey Fernando** district is involving residents in several district related activities and processes through the **municipal Zaragoza Vivienda** company and the **Social Center CEDIS**. Furthermore, the Actur Rey Fernando district is planning to increase energy efficiency in public buildings, public lighting systems, water networks, shared energy production systems between buildings, heat and power cogeneration systems, renewable energy systems and improving mobility systems.

Table 32 - Summary of inhabitants social characteristics - Actur Rey Fernando

Age group	12.43% of the inhabitants are 0-14 years old
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	41.92% of the inhabitants are 15-49 years old
	45.66% of the inhabitants are 50+ years old
Employment rate	Not available
Education	14% of the inhabitants have no education
	29% of the inhabitants have essential education
	23% of the inhabitants have University level
	34% of the inhabitants have Superior studies
Wage band	Not available
Ethnicity	9.5% of the inhabitants are foreigners
	90.5% of the inhabitants are spanish

Comparison of SUPER-i SUPERSHINE Lighthouse Survey and the EUROSTAT statistic findings

Denmark: The feedback from the SUPERSHINE Lighthouse survey on Denmark states that the buildings in FaellesBo district have been renovated twice since its construction in 1958, which is a clear indication of the good status of the buildings. This explains why Denmark has the lowest rate of population with low income who are unable to keep their homes adequately warm during winter and cool during summer. Furthermore, the current quality of the social housing buildings in the district explains why Denmark has the lowest rate for low income households living in dwellings with leaking roofs, damp walls, floors and foundations. Also, the high salary to energy consumption rate per household explains the EUROSTAT findings on Denmark residents having the lowest arrears on utility bills compared to the other investigated countries and the European Union level. This also supports the EUROSTAT findings on Denmark having the lowest living cost overburden rate per household compared to the other countries.

Italy: The responses received from the SUPERSHINE Lighthouse survey on Italy states that the current social housing buildings in Boito district will be demolished and rebuilt due to the poor condition and the amount of work needed to improve the living conditions in this district. This is in line with the findings from the EUROSTAT statistics in table 13, which states that low income households living in poor condition are ranging from 17% to 30% which is quite high compared to the other EU countries. Also, we find that the households unable to keep their homes adequately warm during winter is 60% which is quite large compared to the other EU countries. However, this finding is in line with the EUROSTAT statistics of Table 2, 5 and 6. Finally, the high energy cost to annual salary rate explains why households in Italy are at risk of poverty and social exclusion is high compared to EU countries.

Latvia: The poor state of the buildings in the **Agenskalna priedes** and the heating system installed (does not allow residents to control the temperature within their homes) explains the high rates of the population unable to keep their homes adequately warm during winter and cool during summer compared to the European Union level. Also, according to the social profiling of Latvia, the average income per household is comparatively low compared to the other countries which explains the higher rate of arrears on utility bills. The feedback from the SUPER-i SUPERSHINE lighthouse survey on Latvia, states that since the construction of the buildings in the district in 1960's no renovation or refurbishments were implemented which explains the high rate of low income people living in dwellings with damp walls, floors, foundations and leaking roofs.

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Lastly, the current high heating and electricity consumption in the social housing buildings explains the high final energy consumption per household in Latvia.

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